

D1.7. Deliverable Rural Attractiveness: The Post-Evaluation Update

Project	PoliRural	
Project title:	Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People	
Grant	818496	
Website:	www.polirural.eu	
Contact:	info@polirural.eu	
Version:	0.1	
Date:	15 February 2021	
Responsible:	AREI	
Contributing:	xxx, yyy	
Reviewers:	Pavel Kogut Patrick Crehan Christian Hartmann Antoni Oliva	
Dissemination Level:	Public	X
	Confidential - only consortium members and European Commission Services	
Keywords:	Rural attractiveness, rurality, rural development, regional development, rural and regional policy, LEADER, cultural context, rural typology, policy analysis	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 818496

Revision History

Revision no.	Date	Author	Organization	Description

Responsibility for the information and views set out in this publication lies entirely with the authors.

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

AEZ	Aggregate Environmental Zones
AGZ	Aggregate Geographic Zone
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CLLD	Community-led Local Development
CORINE	Coordination of Information on the Environment
CORINE LANDCOVER	European database of biophysical land use
D1.7	Deliverable 1.7

DEGURBA	Degree of urbanisation
DG Regio	The Commission's Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy
EAGGF	European Agricultural Guidance and Guarantee Fund
EAFRD	European Agriculture Fund for Rural Development
EC	European Commission
EDORA	European Development Opportunities in Rural Areas, Project
EIB	European Investment Bank
EFTA	European Free Trade Area
ELARD	The European Leader Association for Rural Development
ENRD	European Network for Rural Development
EP	European Parliament
ESI	European structural funds
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
EUROSTAT	European Statistical Office
ESF	European Social Fund
ESPON	European Observation Network, Territorial Development and Cohesion
EU	European Union
FAROEU	Foresight Analysis for Rural Areas Of Europe, Project
FUA	Functional Urban Area
GDP	Gross domestic product
GIS	Geographic information system
GVA	Gross value added
HDI	Human Development Index
ICT	Information and communications technology
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LAGs	Local Action Groups
LAU	Local Administrative Unit
LEADER	Liaisons Entre Actions de Development de l'Economie Rurale (Links between actions for the development of the rural economy)
LUZ	Larger Urban Zones
NERD	Neo-endogenous regional development
NACE R2	Statistical Classification of Economic Activities version2
NRP	New Rural Paradigm
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PLUREL	Peri-urban land use relationships, Project
QOL	Quality of life
R&D	Research and development
RDI	Regional development index
RUR	Rural-urban region
SWOT	Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats
T1	Task 1

TERCET	NUTS Regulation in European Union
TiB	Territories in between
TL3	Small regions, OECD classification
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

Report Rural Attractiveness: The Post-Evaluation Update (D1.7) is the third and final edition of a series of deliverables that sought to explore the concept of rural attractiveness and how it varies between regions. The report analysed track and present changes in the definition of rural attractiveness; Explained factors that determine rural attractiveness and Offered areas that can be explored in future research.

The study was based on the important concept of rural attractiveness and rural typology based on the literature review, the existing definition of rural attractiveness was analysed using previous deliverables, the pilot analysis of the selected policy contribution to rural attractiveness was performed (Task 4.5). Finally, recommendations were made for the development and practical implementation of awareness of rural attractiveness.

The literature review was based on the search for new contexts that could complement existing contexts / factors. Politics, different scales, economics of individual and group behaviour, leadership, public service quality issues, symbiosis of different development approaches, cultural context, multifunctional place-based understanding, manifestations of territorial diversity in rural typologies, can complement and create new accents for existing rural attractiveness. The different rural typologies point not so much to the commonalities of rural areas as to their differences. These differences should be respected in the development of common policies for different territories.

Existing definitions of rural areas, the assessment of the development trend make it necessary to emphasize the human scale, motivation, sustainability of ongoing processes, quality of life and wellbeing as necessary factors for understanding rural attractiveness.

The analysis of the pilot policy showed differences in the rural attractiveness of the pillars. This raises the question of the different needs of the territories and the political instruments for addressing them, on the one hand, and the differences between the rural communities itself, on the other. Although rural attractiveness is defined the same for everyone, its understandings and contexts may be different.

Understanding rural attractiveness in the future will depend on the ability of regions to accept and implement it.

Keywords

Rural attractiveness, rurality, rural development, regional development, rural and regional policy, LEADER, cultural context, rural typology, policy analysis

2 Introduction

Report Rural Attractiveness: The Post-Evaluation Update (D1.7) is the third and final edition of a series of deliverables that sought to explore the concept of rural attractiveness and how it varies between regions. Polirural intends to develop an initial definition of rural attractiveness, which will further serve as a basis for pilot needs and policy analysis in the Current Rural Situation (WP4), shaping the Future Rural Outlook (WP5) and Regional Rural Change (WP6). The project envisages an update of rural attractiveness awareness after Post needs analysis (T4.3) and Post-Evaluation Update T4.5). Keeping up with the necessary changes during the project allows to align it closer with the realities on the ground. Conclusions of previous deliverables were influenced by methods and input data used. D1.7 is based on other deliverables already developed. First of all, already in WP1 D.1.1 and D1.4, where the initial definition of rural attractiveness and post needs analysis have been performed. Rural attractiveness is largely determined by needs and their definition, and is therefore closely linked to WP4 D4.2, D4.4, D4.5, where needs analysis was carried out, and D4.5 analysis of the impact of selected policy pilots. (Figure 1)

Figure 1 D1.7 link with other deliverables

Aim of the report:

- Track and present changes in the definition of rural attractiveness
- Explain factors that determine rural attractiveness
- Offer areas that can be explored in future research

This deliverable seeks to update the rural attractiveness's vision or definition, which was created in the first stage of Task 1.1, and 1.4 through: (i) supplementing the literature review on rural development; (ii) analysing needs, rural attractiveness pillars of territorial differences based on T4.2 Stakeholder Mapping; T4.4 Needs-Policy Mapping; T4.5 Evaluation Of Regional Policy Measures.

Key research questions investigated in this deliverable are:

- What are the results of previous deliverables on the definition of rural attractiveness?
- What has been the impact of T4.5 results on the initial definition?
- How should previous tasks be interpreted in relation to rural attractiveness?

Answers to these questions allowed the consortium to:

- Compare changes in pilot positions toward rural attractiveness;
- Assess the need for a new definition, definition changes;
- Contribute to further emphasis on understanding rural attractiveness.

The study has several parts. The first section focuses on rural development and regional development issues, rural typologies based on a literature review. The second section evaluate rural attractiveness

based on previous research. In the third section, the interpretation of rural attractiveness is based on the analysis of pilot area policy. The fourth chapter summarizes the study's findings and recommendations for future changes in rural attractiveness. (Figure 2)

Figure 2 Structure of D1.7

3 Methodology

3.1 Research approach

The development of PolyRural's vision and definition of rural attractiveness is an ongoing process executed in several stages, each of which is based on the results of other project work packages.

The literature review is aimed at the contextual explanation of certain concepts. The concepts complement and extend the literature review performed in the previous stages of defining rural attractiveness (D1.1, D1.4).

The clarification of concepts related to rural attractiveness identifies contexts that can complement the definition. From a variety of contexts, those are selected that can be relevant to understanding rural attractiveness. The selection is based on a previous analysis of rural attractiveness factors (D.1.1).

Based on the obtained contexts, the definition is updated.

The analysis of attractiveness factors is based on the existing definition, pilot needs and priorities and the analysis of selected policies. The aim is to determine how this has influenced rural attractiveness factors through pilot analysis and the literature abstraction of rural attractiveness contexts. Different factors of rural attractiveness and previous results were compared by summarizing and grouping the different elements to be analysed. A more detailed explanation of the approach can be found in the relevant section.

3.2 Methods

A mixed research method approach combining qualitative and quantitative techniques was used to update the initial definition of rural attractiveness. The critical thinking approach (Jackson, 2009) that was used in the first and second stage was also used in research underpinning the D1.7.

Literature review was conducted using qualitative research methods. It was carried out using two review methods: 1) the systematic review approach, using the descriptive and comparative methods (Thomas & Harden, 2008); and 2) integrative review approach including diverse data sources, which enhance a holistic understanding of the topic of interest (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005), like that was used in the D1.1, D1.4. A common approach to the interpretation of meanings of textual data is carried out by means of content analysis (Vaismoradi et al., 2013), which is used as a common approach to the interpretation of meanings from textual data (Seuring & Gold, 2012). De-contextualisation and theory – led abstraction of the content analysis outcomes allow one to claim a certain degree of generalization of the findings.

Figure 4 Concepts link with contexts

The concepts are considered in different contexts, which characterize each of the concepts, expand its understanding and application in the context of rural attractiveness. Based on this, points of view that characterize each set of concepts and selected contexts are considered.

4.1.1 Development

Definition

Both regional development and rural development include the key concept of development. Development is one of the most controversial concepts in the social sciences. The definition of development is contextual.

Often, development is seen as an improvement or as a measure to achieve improvement, or as both. Nederveen Pieterse defines development as improvement and define development as the organized intervention in collective affairs according to a standard of improvement. What constitutes improvement and what is an appropriate intervention obviously varies according to class, culture, historical context and relations of power. Development theory is the negotiation of these issues. (Nederveen Pieterse, 2010) Over time 'development' has carried very different meanings. The understanding of modern development comes from the postwar era of modern development thinking. It includes several contexts - growth, modernity, social, political contexts, which form different theories and approaches.

Scale context

Development can involve understanding with different meanings, depending on the context in which it is used. Development is a normative concept that can be supplemented, changed. Goulet (1971) sees this as a set of changes where the social system moves from a situation that is unsatisfactory to a better situation. (Hoggart, Buller, 2016) Development has an inherent scale. Initially, development has been a western monocultural project. Gradually

development is becoming a multilevel, multiscalar series of efforts, simultaneously taking place at levels lower than the nation, at the national level and at levels beyond the nation. Contemporary development policy is incoherent because the different levels of development action - local, microregional, national, macroregional, international, global - are not adequately articulated. Thus, a comprehensive, holistic approach to development is not only multidimensional but also multiscalar, such that development efforts at different levels are cumulative and interconnect. (Nederveen Pieterse, 2010). Developments can be seen in the interplay of scale (globalization, localization, glocalization).

Growth context

The concept of development has historically been centered in the economics and as such is associated with socio-economic growth. It can be synonymous and yet different. Growth in this context is treated as prosperous, characterized by population growth, employment, income growth, measured, for example, by GDP. However, it equates the concept of development with material values and indicators. In this context, developments lead to widening disparities. Goulet points out that development as a sociological and environmental category should not necessarily be seen as growth, but rather as change (Goulet, 1971).

The context of modernity

Development is often associated with modernity. 'Modernity' in its broadest sense means the condition of being modern, new or up-to-date, i.e. 'the idea of' modernity 'situations people in time' (Ogborn 2005: 339). For some, this diffusion of modernity is interpreted as 'development' and 'progress'. People defining development as 'modernity', look at development largely in economic terms. There are also social benefits associated with economic benefits. The Human Development Index (HDI) seeks to cover economic and social. (Radcliffe 2006; Schech and Haggis 2000).

Modernity has changed over time and can now be questioned in terms of Eurocentric thinking. Development theory moves towards actor - oriented, agency, institutions, constructivism, interpretative, turn, differentiating, plural, polycentrism, multipolarity. Nederveen Pieterse asks about the development trend in various manifestations of modernity (Nederveen Pieterse, 2010). In the 21st century, development is more determined by multiple modernity (Nederveen Pieterse, 2016).

Development theories

There have been several theories of development over time. In the 1950s, modernization theory predicted that everyone should achieve the European model. 1960-70s it was complemented by Dependency theory, which focused on national assistance and governance to the southern (lagging) countries to achieve development. 1980-2000s - neoliberalism - orientation towards market regulation, in the 1990s - postdevelopment - colonialism and Eurocentrism, Sustainable development, culture and development, in the 2000s - globalization, sustainable development, post-development, grassroots approaches, rights -

based development . (Willis, 2011) (see Appendices 1, 2, 3). At present, although a certain theory dominates, different development approaches are used alongside it.

Social context

Development is rooted in Western culture, requires the integration of Western values and behaviours that often ignore traditional cultural values. Traditionally, development in this context focuses on the individual as a driver of development. Development is also defined as freedom (Sen, 1999). Social and cultural norms and expectations need to be considered in their own right are also important (Radcliffe 2006; Schech and Haggis 2000). Ethnicity and religion are important in determining our behaviour. A new field is emerging - development ethics. The development of long time has been understood as modernization and western - ization and studied as an economic issue. Currently, the economy is reintegrating ethics in its conceptualization, methodology, and analysis. (Goulet, 1997; Hoggart, Buller, 2016)

Political context

There is the question of development as a theory and its political and social interpretation. Is development theory a matter of social science or of politics? Writers have different views on the degree of autonomy of development theory. Development thinking is its policyoriented character. Different stakeholders have different takes on what development means and how to achieve it. Nederveen Pieterse emphasizes that this is not a minor point but a fundamental circumstance. (Nederveen Pieterse, 2010).

Smart growth and sustainable development

Development in the context of growth is linked to a number of policy concepts where knowledge and innovation are important as driving forces. Regional and place-based policies are crucial preconditions for obtaining smart growth, taking into account their diversity in terms of economic conditions, knowledge, and innovation capacity). This is in turn highly dependent on business culture, workforce skills, education and training institutions, innovation support services, R&D and information and communications technology (ICT) infrastructure. (Nadli et al., 2015)

The concept of sustainable development was originally a symbolic, pro-growth, environmental concept that is now much broader. The idea of inclusive growth is a concept that relates to the creation of employment and social cohesion in lagging urban and rural areas. (Nadli et al., 2015)

4.1.2 Rural Development

Rural development includes rural and development concepts. The concept of rural (rurality) is in a dual context with the concept of urban. Uncertainties arise in the urban-rural distinction itself, which is territorially different, socially, politically (in regulation) conditional, changing over time. Rural development encompasses the concept of development in rural areas. Rural development includes several contexts, sectors - places, quality of life, connection of

landscapes, cities and rural areas, policies, growth, process of change, rural and agricultural contexts, and importance of innovation.

Rural Definition

There is no common understanding of rural areas in different countries and in the EU as a whole. In order to develop a comparative understanding based on policy objectives and the need for analysis, OECD rural areas are defined on the basis of the following criteria: population density and distance from major urban centers. Rural areas can be further characterized according to various additional criteria stemming from different aspects of rurality - geographical, social, economic and cultural, resulting in different geographic coverage, with important policy implications. (Diakosavvas, 2006)

The concept of countryside is vague and attempts to define boundaries are related to polarity - countryside - city, urban - rural. In the first case it is a division more territorial, in the second - social. Territorial can include social concepts and rural understandings. Rural definitions are based on socio-cultural, employment and ecological criteria. None of them are absolute and more dependent on arbitrary. (Hoggart & Buller, 2016)

Changes of rural definition

Understanding of the countryside changes over time. According to Cloke (2006), it is possible to recognize three significant theoretical frames for conceptualizing rurality: functional, political-economic, and social constructionist. Since the 1950s, rural understanding has evolved from elements of place, landscape and society, land uses in the 1970s to include a new set of dimensions: accessibility, employment, housing, land use, recreation and rural planning; 1980s - be more theoretically informed and policy-oriented; 1990s including privatization, counter-urbanization, gentrification, poverty, accessibility and citizenship as an arena for experience; 2000s, seen as a “threat” to the countryside (urbanization, agribusiness, new fashion of recreation, second homes, class recomposition, etc.) (Cloke, 2006: 20).

Rural-urban relations

The Espon project Urban-rural relations in Europe emphasizes that the new urban-rural relationship is far more complex than the traditional simple reciprocal exchanges between cities and villages. The literature emphasizes mutual interdependency, interconnection. This focus on urban-rural continuum is justified by the visible and invisible flows of people, capital, goods, information and technology between urban and rural areas. (Urban-Rural, 2006)

Despite the large differences between urban and rural areas, diversity within rural areas is increasing but the distinction between “the rural” and “the urban” is becoming blurred. (Friedland 2002; Torre, Wallet, 2016).

Rural development trends

The very concept of rural attractiveness includes attitudes and collective understanding of the countryside. Indeed, the words and phrases countryside, wilderness, outback, periphery, farm

belt, village, hamlet, bush, peasant society, pastoral, garden, unincorporated territory, open space, refer to different and sometimes conflicting conceptions of rural land. The term “rural” must now be considered alongside the term “peri-urban” in order to define areas where there are various degrees of interpenetration of city and country, but without a clear distinction between the two. (Torre, Wallet, 2016)

Torre, Wallet distinguishes between a functional understanding of the countryside characterized by the type of farming, the structure of the land, the characteristics of the population, the relationship with nature, and the behavioral qualities associated with living in the countryside; Economic awareness associated with certain structural problems affecting populations, such as the environment for tourism development, the living environment for retirees, accessibility problems; Social construction. (Torre, Wallet, 2016)

When creating a rural typology, it leaves an impact on the attitude towards the territory. Such rural stereotypes have often been quite negative, and have included, for example: The agrarian countryside, The rural exodus, Rural dependency culture (from support), Rural labor markets, associated with segmentation, barriers to entrepreneurship (Copus, Noguera, 2010). Although these characteristics are present in many places, not in all cases.

Understanding the countryside is influenced by the processes that take place in the countryside. Torre, Wallet emphasizes that nowadays rural areas are facing two fundamental types of change, suggesting that there is no longer a dominant model: they are subject to increasingly strong influence from cities and urban populations; competition for natural resources located in rural areas plays a key role in current development policies. (Torre, Wallet, 2016)

The rural economy is no longer a farm economy; "Rural" vs. "urban" is more than a simple dichotomy. There is a strong interdependence; Consumption of natural amenities has become one of the primary determinants of rural growth; Sector-based policies are neither efficient nor effective rural development policies; Rural development is a general equilibrium problem that requires general equilibrium tools (Horlings, L.G. & Marsden, 2014)

Definition of rural development

Rural development is more often seen as a politically determined change in the countryside, on the one hand, and the process of change itself without intervention, on the other. / Harriss (1982) pp. 14-15./ It is often used as a substitute for “rural development policy”, “is often used interchangeably with regional policy or used in relation to traditional agricultural policies and environmental policy (Diakosavvas, 2006). Understanding rural development is often rooted in the growth paradigm. Rural development are actions aimed mainly at the social and economic development of rural areas (Chigbu, 2012), including “sustainable economic growth and improved living conditions, bringing rural areas up to national standards of development, and ensuring that rural regions are attractive places to live” (Woods, 2011: 131). The current

trend is slowly shifting towards a more progressive humanistic direction. (Brauer & Dymitrow, 2014)

Thus, the concept of rural development moves towards the exploitation of rural advantages and presenting diversity of regions as a valuable feature and not an obstacle that should seek to overcome. This need for sustained reorientation in economic understanding and policy strategies, placing 'social innovation', sustainable resource use and well-being 'higher' than economic growth. (Dax & Fischer, 2018) Rural development is seen not only as a specific business, but rural life can invoke a sense of community, of working together, and social change. These efforts exhibit holistic traits, such as "sustaining local services, maintaining the local population, reducing negative climate impacts of long car journeys through providing local services and employment, and sustaining local community events, social capital and a strong sense of local identity" (Steiner and Atterton 2015, p. 43).

Rural development as a sector and as a place defined

Rural development is no longer identified as a sectoral policy. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) is ultimately determining that it was a place-based question rather than a topic best dealt with through the imposition of policies (2003) (Torre, Wallet, 2016)

Rural development as a multidimensional process

Torre & Wallet sees rural development as a multidimensional process, in the form of different practices, some of which are still developing and may be interconnected (landscape management, nature conservation, agritourism, organic farming, specific agricultural products, short food-supply chains, etc.) in such a way that elements considered superfluous in the modernist paradigm acquire new roles in the relations between farms, and between farmers and urban populations. (Torre, Wallet, 2016). At the same time, the present state of rural development is not primarily farm-focused; considerable emphasis has been placed on what is an increasingly interdependent continuum between rural and urban places. (Atkinson, 2017)

Rural development is linked to quality of life

Rural development is associated with 'Quality of life' (QOL), which includes many material and immaterial aspects. It refers to the general well-being of people, groups or societies. It should be emphasized that QOL does not simply refer to income-related living standards of individuals (the economic aspect), but is a broader concept that also includes the surrounding environment, physical and mental health, education, leisure, recreation, social belonging, and so forth (Brauer & Dymitrow, 2014) Quality of life in a specific domain has spillover effects.

Rural development policy

Taking into account the concept of sustainability, rural development policy can be based on three directions: to strengthen the competitiveness of businesses, sectors and territories by

providing support to innovation initiatives; to address environmental challenges, through the implementation of measures and regulations that contribute to the conservation and development of natural resources, the preservation of biodiversity, and climate change adaptation; interventions adopted to help maintain the quality of life in rural areas are to a certain extent giving way to measures aimed at addressing the dire social, health and employment situations of certain categories of rural populations in territories severely hit by the recession. (Torre, Wallet , 2016).

Re-territorialization

Given the shifts in rural development and rural awareness in the last decades, Re-territorialization is an important dimension of what the OECD, postulate as the 'New Rural Paradigm' (NRP) in Europe. According to the OECD, this paradigm includes a new, multisector, place-based approach to rural development that claims a need for closer links between the rural and urban economy, and to see rural development as a close interplay with regional development more generally. (OECD, 2006). (Horlings, L.G. & Marsden, 2014)

The term "rural policy" is also used to reduce peripherality (Copus et al., 2011). Peripherality forms not only the loss of population in itself but the impacts on rural society and economy (Brown & Argent, 2016).

Growth paradigm

The overwhelming majority of policy objectives for rural regions is still oriented towards traditional 'growth' paradigms. Policies focusing on sustainability, ecological modernization, public goods, multifunctionality, rural restructuring, networks and globalization, and indigeneity and the circular economy are changing important aspects of the challenges in rural development policies. The scope of understanding the concepts themselves is also changing. Sustainable development includes not only environmental issues, but also human and social development, including human rights, good governance and solidarity. (Horlings & Padt, 2011). However, despite many changes and new policy challenges, the growth paradigm remains dominant.

Rural development policies are characterized by a large "time lag". As early as 1988, the EC communication "The future of rural society" set out rural development policies (messages): rural diversity, the role of non-agricultural sectors, the role of social and environmental development in rural development, integrated vision and coordination. (Copus & De Lima, 2015) The future policy of the EU, the European Commission (2010) addresses 'smart, sustainable and inclusive growth', which includes the classical, key concerns for future development, requires a comprehensive approach that goes beyond economic growth (Dax & Fischer, 2018)

Rural and agricultural policy

Traditionally, rural and agricultural development policy has been the subject of discussion for some time to understand the extent to which agricultural policies are coherent with rural

development policies and with broader, economy-wide policies. The trend is that agriculture policy has a modest impact on the future viability of rural areas. A one-size-fits-all approach to rural policy does not exist. The heterogeneity of rural areas 'challenges and potentials call for tailor-made policies. Governance issues are becoming important. Diakosavvas points out that despite new rural development trends and differences in the definition of rural areas, policies can ignore large areas, such as the urban fringe, where the countryside meets and the city where the majority of the rural population lives. (Diakosavvas, 2006)

Social contexts of rural development

The social and local components of rural development are becoming increasingly important. The driving force of development then lies in the occurrence of localized innovation or knowledge spillovers within the local system. (Torre, Wallet, 2016) The importance of collective learning, co-ordination and communication processes between different actors in teams, actor networks and other means of co-operation that are new in relation to the horizon of experiences of the people concerned.

Scientists have put forward local and local resource-based development as an approach to achieving rural development challenges. However, it should be noted that Neo-endogenous regional development (NERD) is only successful if it also builds upon, encourages and supports the development of social innovations. The success of NERD processes is strongly dependent on people's ability to develop sustainable structures, and in doing to establish a balance that, on the one hand, facilitates all forms of innovation, creativity, new ideas and visions in acting, and, on the other hand, maintains necessary stability. (Neumeier, 2011) In addition, the role of public-private partnerships in the context of local rural development is important, involving stakeholders in the decision-making process (Bjärstig and Sandström 2017), which can ensure stability and sustainability. The role of social contacts and social innovation in transforming rural areas and exploiting development opportunities is increasingly emphasized. (Dax & Fischer, 2018).

LEADER

The LEADER Initiative has developed as a form of public involvement, a development-stimulating approach, and a territorially based development policy. The Community Initiative LEADER (a French acronym for 'Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Economie Rurale') aims to stimulate rural development initiatives by helping rural associations, local authorities and rural action groups (LAGs) to devise innovative strategies for local development. It also helps local people acquire the skills that are needed for establishing integrated strategies based on the realization of local potentials.

The context of Leader history

The LEADER approach began in the 1980s with the revision of 'classic' development approaches, which were based on essentially 'top down' policies and, in most cases, on

undifferentiated sectoral interventions designed to apply the 'urban' model, or the model of the most dynamic areas, across the board.

The 'area-based' approach, based on involving local communities and adding value to local resources, gradually came to be seen as a new way of creating jobs and businesses in rural areas. In this new approach, considerable effort is placed on integration, participation and empowerment. (Courades, Brosei, 2018)

LEADER developed from the early 1990s a pilot program with 217 LAGs and a funding of € 0.5 billion for their mainstream policy with more of 3000 LAGs and a minimum. 5% of the EAFRD (see Annex 4). LEADER I was an innovative and relatively small program managed directly by the European Commission and targeted towards most deprived rural areas. LEADER II Community Initiative (1994-99). 102 "Operational Programs (OPs) were implemented by national or regional managing authorities from the ERDF, ESF and EAGGF. During the period 2000-06, the application of the LEADER approach was extended to a wider range of rural areas. This refers to the fact that the whole rural territory of the EU is considered a target area, and networks have taken up a central role, including transnational cooperation. The ambition of the LEADER + Community Initiative was to reach a maturity level (Courades, Brosei, 2018). From 2017, LEADER was implemented as a LEADER rural development axis, from 2014 as an RDP measure 19, providing support for the preparation, and implementation of local strategies, cooperation measures and support for the maintenance of LAG activities.

LEADER principles

The approach itself is primarily defined by 7 key principles, which are: area - based local development strategies, bottom-up elaboration and implementation of strategies, local public - private partnerships - LAGs, integrated and multi-sector actions, innovation, cooperation and networking (EC Regulation 1698/2005, EU regulation 1305 / 2013).

LEADER also promotes trans-national co-operation and the exchange of relevant information and experience through a European rural development network.

LEADER positive and negative

Overall in the literature there are positive assessments regarding fields like a better cooperation, participation, networking, partly - innovation, linkage between different types of knowledge, mobilization of actors and suitable projects fitting to the local areas. The LEADER approach and the conditions of EU funding allow to support small producers, to create local infrastructure necessary for the local community, to support social activities in local communities, creation and dissemination of local knowledge.

The earlier funding periods have given more freedom to the local level. An enhancement of bureaucratic settings was particularly related to the mainstreaming of LEADER as a part of the EAFRD (Polleman et al. 2014) To some extent, the more formalized approach has somewhat watered down the original bottom up approach (Urban - Rural, 2006) , which will continue in recent programming periods. The European Court of Auditors (ECA) adopted in 2010 a highly

critical report on the implementation of LEADER, particularly weak performance for LEADER added values, creating innovations. Is need to allow LAGs to develop local solutions that do not correspond to the rural development program measures, but allow to implement own LAGs local needs (Courades, Brosei, 2018)

Despite the critics, LEADER's wide scale success in the EU's rural areas has inspired other EU Funds to extend the application of this approach in other areas. The LEADER approach has been further broadened through Community-led Local Development (CLLD) - a territorial policy instrument that supports the mobilization of local potentials at the sub-regional and local levels in rural, fishery and urban territories. Multi-ESI Funds (multi-fund approach) are used - European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), European Social Fund (ESF), European Agricultural Guidance and Guarantee Fund (EAGGF), European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and other financial instruments such as the European Investment Bank (EIB), thus becoming an integral part of EU rural policy.

4.1.3 Regional development

Regional development includes two major contextual views - the regional / territorial / view, which is often used as local and regional development. Different territorial scales are underlined here. The second view is a policy view focused on territorial change. This is understood as actions that change the situation, both economic and environmental and social.

The contexts of the concept of regional development are territorial development, including rural development, policy (regional policy), policy approaches and theories, spatial-blind versus place based approach, context of growth and change.

Definition of regional development

Regional development is related to development studies. Björn Hettne defines it as a practical, problem-oriented and interdisciplinary field that focuses on the analysis of social change in a global context, taking into account the historical, cultural, ecological, etc. Local and regional development studies have traditionally been led by distribution in northern developed countries and southern lagging countries and regions. (Pike et al., 2017b) This has changed significantly in recent decades.

Development studies are related to other fields of science, such as political science, sociology, economics, international relations, anthropology and geography. In the context of a policy-oriented approach, regional development is a broad term but can be seen as a general effort to reduce regional disparities by supporting (employment and wealth-generating) economic activities in regions. (see Annex 5) In the past, regional development policy tended to try to achieve these objectives by means of large-scale infrastructure development and by attracting inward investment. Past policies have failed to reduce regional disparities significantly and have not been able to help individual lagging regions to catch up, despite the allocation of significant public funding. The result is under-used economic potential and weakened social cohesion (OECD, 2020).

Therefore, the implications and scope of regional development may vary according to the definition of a region.

Growth and wellbeing

Local and regional development has historically been dominated by economic concerns and, fundamentally, by growth. Growth is not always the objective per se, but a means for achieving well-being, according to the social, economic, cultural and political conditions of particular populations in specific places. (Pike et al., 2017b) The distinction between development and growth has often disappeared. The explanation lies in the way development is defined. There are distinctions to be made between qualities that are 'instrumentally significant', such as jobs and income, and qualities and 'capabilities' that are 'intrinsically significant', such as health, education and civic participation. Such a distinction encourages a focus on matters of well-being and quality of life, the conditions of 'human flourishing', and whether and how growth can be rendered more equitable, inclusive and just (Benner & Pastor, 2012; Rodríguez-Pose & Wilkie, 2015).

This is also reflected in the indicators for measuring regional development. In addition to Gross domestic produce (GDP) per capita, for example, human development index (HDI), regional development index (RDI) are used. Applying HDI, RDI, includes measures of a healthy life, knowledge, economic standard of living and employment, also changes the assessment of regions relative to GDP. The use of formal indicators does not always justify objectives, especially if they are aimed at the wellbeing of the population. Pike asks the question: 'what kind of regional development and for whom?' (Pike et al., 2017b)

Regional development policy

Regional development can also be understood as a policy process, that is, changes over time in a given area based on specific measures. In this sense, regional development can be equated with rural development if the area is rural. Sometimes regional development is seen in a broader context, encompassing the whole of society, without dividing it into urban and rural areas, including issues of territorial governance, different sectoral policies that affect territories.

An integrated approach to regional policy

In its paper, the European Community emphasized the need for an integrated regional approach in The future of rural society (EC, 1988). Past experience of infrastructure underutilization and overutilization in the Community has clearly demonstrated that excessive concentration on infrastructures in regional policy is invisible, even in the least developed regions. Infrastructures must be used as an integrated instrument for overall development. (EC, 1988)

Barca emphasizes the role of infrastructure not only as a precondition for development, but also something demanded by society, highly visible and extremely attractive for decision-makers, it is politically beneficial. Even if the aggregate impact of infrastructure policies has

sometimes been positive, they have often led to greater economic agglomeration, regional polarization, and to an increasing economic marginalization of many peripheral regions where significant infrastructure investments have taken place (Barca et al. 2012).

Policy changes in regional development

Regional development as a separate field was established in the 20th century. In the 1950s emphasis was placed on the impact of business performance on economic indicators. At the end of the 1990s, the regional development approach became multidisciplinary. Different branches of science tried to answer the question of how the region developed under the influence of various factors.

A combination of shifting social, economic, environmental and political processes, changed development thinking, policy and practice. Some have characterized this qualitative transformation as a shift from an 'old' paradigm of regional development that sought to compensate lagging regions to a 'new' growth-oriented paradigm (eg Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2009b; Camagni and Capello, 2015; Garcilazo et al., 2015), commonly labeled 'place-based development policy'. (see Annex6)

Place-based versus spatial – blind.

The transition from the old to the new approach was gradual and influenced by a number of important studies in this field. The most influential publications are the World Bank's (2009) World Development Report Reshaping Economic Geography; 2004 Sapir Report An Agenda for a Growing Europe; Barca (2009) report "An Agenda for a Reformed Cohesion Policy"; The OECD (2009a) report "How regions grow"; Local development: toward a new protagonism of cities and regions (CAF, 2010).

The World Bank's (2009) report and Sapir Report express "spatially-blind" strategies. Barca (2009) report, the OECD (2009a) report and the CAF (2010) report suggested place-based policies approaches. The reports emphasized the role of local solutions in the development of potential, the development potential of each region, and the role of institutions and governance in local development. Exogenous policy action is seen as a way to trigger endogenous changes. (Barca et al. 2012)

Place-based link with spatial-blind approach

Barca emphasizes the importance of a place-based approach in development, whereby context here is understood in terms of its social, cultural, and institutional characteristics. Space-neutral policies always affect a place / region, many of which will undermine the aims of the policy itself unless its spatial effects are explicitly taken into consideration. The place-based approach also focuses on the issue of knowledge in policy intervention. (Barca et al. 2012) Locally created and implemented policies provide public goods aimed at improving the local business environment: skills, technology and clusters (Barca, McCann, & Rodríguez-Pose, 2012; see also OECD, 2012). (see Annex 7) The OECD warns that there is a limit to policy interventions at the local, regional and / or city regional levels.

OECD (2012) has sought to draw together the elements of a 'new' paradigm that emphasizes a bottom-up initiative and responsibility, and the reconfiguration of center and center – regional / local relations toward self-sustaining / self-financing forms of development . (Pike et al., 2017b; Pike et al., 2017a). Place-based policies are not a substitute for appropriate structural policies. In practice, both policies tend to operate simultaneously. There are risks: a territorial-based policy is a risk of inadequate investment, a space-blind policy is a past experience that investments have not benefited certain areas. (Purgalis & Gray, 2016)

In addition, it should be noted that many other approaches to regional development are used, such as people-centered models, active regional development and space-blind policies (see Bentley and Pugalís, 2014), as different modes of regional development vie for attention.

Regional policy as a horizontal policy

Regional development can be perceived as a horizontal “policy of policies”. Regional development policy at the national level does not consist of a fixed set of policies. Rather, it consists of strategies to support the coherent implementation of various policies, such as housing, transport, employment, economic development, innovation, energy, welfare, education, land use, policies. The OECD recognizes that most structural policies are place-blind, which does not take into account the specificities of territories. As a result, not all regions are equally affected by structural reforms. In several developed countries, productivity growth is declining, in other regions of developed countries, there is a decline. Regions closer to cities reduce the gap with cities, but further away, this is not the case. Economic theory can only partly explain large and persistent productivity and employment differences across regions. (OECD (2019)

Rural policy 3.0

In 2016, the New Rural Paradigm was updated with the Rural Policy 3.0, which reflects the new knowledge acquired in the intervening decade. The core idea in Rural Policy 3.0 is that economic growth occurs in different ways in rural areas than it does in urban ones. The rural growth process takes place in a “low-density economy” where agglomeration effects do not occur and distance plays an important role in production costs and the lives of the people. (OECD (2019) (see Annex 8)

4.1.4 Cultural context and behavioural economics

Rising inequality

Inequalities between regions have been growing in recent decades, according to the OECD. (OECD, 2018) The gap within countries between the top 10% regions with the highest labor productivity and the bottom 75% has grown on average by almost 60% over the last two decades. The Seventh Cohesion Report also points out that quality of life, and quality of governance and institutions is a fundamental precondition for growth at the subnational level.

The report finds that improvements in the quality of institutions appear to be consistently important factors underlying economic growth in EU regions. (OECD, 2018)

The role of personal motivation in development processes

As widespread theory cannot always explain regional development differences, governments from different parts of the world have focused their attention on integrating behavioral insights into the policy-making process to make public policies work better (OECD, 2018).

In this context, it becomes important to be the “right” people engaged; Are the “right” people / activities funded? Are the funds used appropriately?

Theory (Deci, Olafsen and Ryan, 2017), a macro theory of human motivation, emphasizes the role of human motivation, to perform at a high level requires psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness (i.e. relationships with other people). The challenge is how to organize to make these needs work (OECD, 2018).

Studies argue that in interpreting regions, discontent individual differences in attitudes are more important than material differences (Gordon, 2018) and interregional differences are more significant than individual differences (Rodriguez-Pose, 2018). Where these economic patterns of inter-regional inequality overlap with cultural and attitudinal factors, feelings of economic neglect and cultural concerns reinforce each other up to the point where large shares of the population reject the dominant political consensus. Improvements in living standards that affect the material side do not change the perception of cultural loss in communities where work has been a source of pride and cultural identity (Ulrich-Schad and Duncan, 2018).

Cultural and social factors are also a reason why a sole focus on increasing labor mobility will not be sufficient to address the geography of discontent. Many people in economically struggling regions are rooted in their local community and prefer to stay even if this brings economic disadvantages. The OECD states that without a change towards policies that are more sensitive to regional conditions, regional disparities will now likely only get worse. (OECD, 2019)

Individual and collective role in development

Economic geography, political economy has returned to look for answers to the question of how individual and collective behavior determines the results of regional development (Huggins and Thompson, 2016; Lee, 2017). Behavioral economists have sought to integrate psychological theories of behavior as a means of explaining economic action. The emergence of a ‘new sociology of development’ combines the role of geography with factors relating to individual and collective behavior (Sachs, 2000; Tubadji and Nijkamp, 2015). Furthermore, scholars have increasingly highlighted the role of institutions in fostering regional development. (Huggins & Thomson, 2019) No explicit attention has been given to the geographic perspective, and to the role of socio-institutional (ie local actors, stakeholders and governance structures) and territorial (ie geographic and socioeconomic situation) contexts

(Ilbery, 1986; Robinson, 2004; Zasada et al., 2017). Finally, leadership embedded in social capital, defined here as networks of people built on trust, cooperation, energy and commitment to sustainability, is important (Horlings & Padt, 2011).

The concept of culture in space and social environment

Individual and groups behavior rooted in most wide cultural contexts. The concept of culture generally refers to the way in which people behave, often as a result of their background and group affiliation. Huggins & Thomson emphasizes that the socio-spatial culture of cities and regions consists of the ways and means by which individuals and groups within place-based communities interact and shape their environment. (Huggins & Thomson, 2019)

Socio-spatial culture refers to the broader societal traits and relations that underpin places in terms of prevailing mind-sets and the overall way of life within these places (Huggins and Thompson, 2015). It principally constitutes the social structure and features of group life within cities and regions that can generally be considered to be beyond the economic life of such places (Huggins and Thompson, 2016).

It is important how regional development (policy) takes cultural differences into account. The regional development process is heavily threatened by a weak understanding of the regional culture of entrepreneurship which prioritizes a linear cause – effect relationship and favorite financial austerity approaches, applying a strict neo-classical policy logic. This perspective ignores the interrelated effects of public, private and civic action and does not pay sufficient attention to innovation, networks, migration and mobility, and infrastructure as overarching themes for shaping regional development (Turok et al., 2017).

Alternative development perspectives

There are other views on development. Development objectives can be opened up to local assessment and it becomes possible to imagine many different development pathways that build on local assets, experience and expectations (Gibson-Graham, 2010) taking into account the cultural context of different regions.

4.2 Territorial typologies

Different territorial and policy approaches require different regions to be defined and distinguished. There are different classifications of regions. They are always linked to the purpose for which they are intended. Regional types are receiving particular attention by policy makers due to policy developments in relation to EU Cohesion Policy, the Treaty of Lisbon and the description of the European goal of territorial cohesion. The study did not attempt to summarize all typologies. The typologies discussed here serve as examples for defining regional differences. Emphasis was placed on the typologies that form the basis of the generally accepted EUROSTAT classifications.

4.2.1 OECD classifications

The OECD classification was developed in the early 1990s with a three-way classification (predominantly urban; intermediate; predominantly rural) based on the population density of districts. (LAU2)

Other classifications were based on the OECD classification, supplemented by other criteria, their combinations (see, for example, JRC, 2009, JRC, 2007). The OECD classification did not cover the diversity of rural areas. There is a doubt that the traditional way of thinking “rural” as the same of “agricultural” may not be true anymore for developed countries (Bollman, 2007)

To improve the OECD approach, various indicators were included: Economic activities including agriculture; Socio-economic structural characteristics; Spatial dimension of social organization; Natural characteristics (Pizzoli, 2007)

Advanced OECD classification

In 2009, the OECD extended its classification to include the remoteness dimension. The new urban-rural typology developed by the Commission takes the OECD approach based on districts and TL3 regions and applies it to population grid cells and to NUTS 3 regions.

The new urban-rural typology developed by the Commission does not include the remoteness dimension. OECD classification creates five categories of NUTS 3 regions:

1. predominantly urban regions;
2. intermediate regions, close to a city;
3. intermediate, remote regions;
4. predominantly rural regions, close to a city;
5. predominantly rural, remote regions.

All predominantly urban regions are considered close to a city. A predominantly rural or intermediate regions is considered remote if less than half of its residents can drive to the centre of a city of at least 50 000 inhabitants within 45 minutes. If more than half of the regions population can reach a city of at least 50 000, it is considered close to a city. (Brezzi et al. 2011; Dijkstra & Poelman, 2011)

4.2.2 Classifications of specific areas

Metro regions

This typology was first presented in the Green Paper on Territorial Cohesion and subsequently in a Regional Focus by Dijkstra. They are approximations of the Larger Urban Zones (LUZs) as used in the Urban Audit. The typology distinguishes three types of metro regions:

1. Capital city regions;

2. Second-tier metro regions;

3. Smaller metro regions.

Border regions

This classification is based on the 2007-2013 cross-border cooperation programmes. Two main types of border regions can be distinguished:

1. internal border regions – these regions are located on borders between EU Member States and/or European Free Trade Area (EFTA) countries;

2. external borders – these regions participate in programmes involving countries outside both the EU and EFTA.

Mountain areas

The typology was prepared for the Green Paper on Territorial Cohesion. Mountain regions at NUTS 3 level are defined as regions in which more than 50% of the surface is covered by topographic mountain areas, or in which more than 50% of the regional population lives in these topographic mountain areas. The typology of NUTS 3 mountain regions distinguishes 3 categories:

1. regions with more than 50% of their population living in mountain areas;

2. regions with more than 50% of their surface covered by mountain areas;

3. regions with more than 50% of their surface covered by mountain areas, and with more than 50% of their population living in mountain areas.

Island territories

Islands were defined by a Eurostat publication study 'Portrait of the Island' in 1994, which excluded islands with a national capital. This was subsequently used in a DG REGIO study to define island regions. Island regions are NUTS 3 regions entirely covered by islands. In this context, islands are defined as territories having:

- a minimum surface of 1 km²;
- a minimum distance between the island and the mainland of 1 km;
- a resident population of more than 50 inhabitants;
- no fixed link (bridge, tunnel, dyke) between the island and the mainland.

The typology of NUTS 3 island regions distinguishes five categories, depending on the size of the major island related to the NUTS 3 region:

1. regions where the major island has less than 50 000 inhabitants;

2. regions where the major island has between 50 000 and 100 000 inhabitants;

3. regions where the major island has between 100 000 and 250 000 inhabitants;

4. regions corresponding to an island with 250 000 to 1 million inhabitants, or being part of such an island;

5. regions being part of an island with at least 1 million inhabitants.

Sparsely populated regions

Sparsely-populated regions are regions with a population density below a certain threshold. Paragraph 30(b) of the Guidelines on national regional aid for 2007-2013 defines low population density regions as ‘areas made up essentially of NUTS 2 geographic regions with a population density of less than 8 inhabitants per km², or NUTS 3 geographic regions with a population density of less than 12.5 inhabitants per km²’. In the Cohesion Report, the analysis was based on the NUTS 3 regions. (Dijkstra & Poelman, 2011)

4.2.3 Other classifications

ESPON project 2000-2006

ESPON 2006 project 1.1.2. “Urban-rural relations in Europe” typology is based on the idea of two main dimensions, that is, degree of urban influence on the one hand, and degree of human intervention on the other hand. Urban influence is here defined according to population density and status of the leading urban centre of each NUTS3 area. Land cover is supposed to reflect both the degree of human intervention and actual land use. Degree of human intervention was determined by the relative share of land cover according to the main land cover classes of the CORINE data set. The six types are:

1. High urban influence, high human intervention
2. High urban influence, medium human intervention
3. High urban influence, low human intervention
4. Low urban influence, high human intervention
5. Low urban influence, medium human intervention
6. Low urban influence, low human intervention (Urban – rural, 2006)

EDORA project

The so-called “EDORA cube” therefore comprises three typologies, reflecting three distinct dimensions of variation (Annex 9). The three typologies attempt to capture the following aspects of rural differentiation:

(i) *Rurality/accessibility*. This typology relates to the Rural-Urban meta-narrative, and was developed (by Dijkstra and Poelman [2008] at DG Regio) from the OECD typology. Four types of (non-urban) regions are distinguished; Intermediate Accessible, Intermediate Remote, Predominantly Rural Accessible, and Predominantly Rural Remote.

(ii) Economic Restructuring. This typology relates to both the Agri-Centric and Global Competition meta-narratives, and was developed from 13 indicators, using a multi-criteria, disaggregative approach. Again four types of non-urban regions were distinguished: Agrarian, Consumption Countryside, Diversified (with strong secondary sector) and Diversified (with strong market services sector).

(iii) Performance. This typology places regions on a continuum between “accumulation” and “depletion”. The performance typology derives its rationale mainly from the Rural-Urban metanarrative.

It is based upon a synthetic index of performance, incorporating 5 indicators. Four types of region are distinguished; Accumulating, Above Average, Below Average, and Depleting. (Copus & Noguera, 2010; Copus & Hörnström, 2011; EDORA, 2011)

PLUREL project

The typology is based on functional regions and urban – rural relationships. Typology represent Rural–urban Regions (RUR) spatially. Covering the territory of European Union (EU), this typology classifies regions into different types, considering city size, degree of regional mono- and poly-centricity, as well as their urban, peri-urban or rural predominance. The development of the typology includes a further delineation of regions into urban, peri-urban and rural sub-regions, all based on land use patterns and population distribution and density. (Zasada et al. 2013)

The peri-urban area includes both the urban fringe and urban periphery. This is defined for the PLUREL project as: ‘discontinuous built development containing settlements of each less than 20,000 population, with an average density of at least 40 persons per hectare (averaged over 1km cells)’ (Loibl & Köstl, 2008; Pierr et al., 2011) (Annex 10)

The PLUREL project focuses on two classifications: The peri-urban is a zone of transitions between urban settlements and their rural hinterland. Project introduce concepts and definitions of the peri-urban within the wider context of the ‘rural-urban region’.

Functional Urban Area (FUA): “an urban core and the area around it that is economically integrated with the centre, e.g. the local labour market. Belonging to a commuter catchment area, FUAs represent common local labour and housing markets.” (ESPON, 2005)

Rural-urban region (RUR): “spatial clusters of three interrelated regional subsystems – the urban core, the periurban surroundings and the rural hinterland. Areas of recreational use, food supply and nature conservation located in predominantly rural areas are also part of the ruralurban region.” (PLUREL, 2011)

Moriconi-Ebrard classification

More narrowly addressing poly-centricity questions, Moriconi-Ebrard (1994) developed a typology of “Regional types of urban–rural spatial patterns” for the NUTS2/3 level. The analysis focused on population distribution and densities in urban and rural areas as well as

on distances between centres and settlement size distribution. As a result, he distinguished amongst “regions dominated by a large metropolis”, “polycentric regions with high urban and rural densities”, “polycentric regions with high urban densities”, “rural areas under metropolitan influence”, “rural areas with networks of medium-sized and small towns” and “remote rural areas”. (Zasada et al. 2013). Ir citas klasifikācijas, kas balstoties uz OECD, veidotas NUTS2 reģioniem (skat. piemēram, De Beer et al., 2014)

FAROEU

EU FP6 Specific Targeted Research Project FAROEU (Foresight Analysis for Rural Areas Of Europe) developed typology view definition of rurality in a two dimensional matrix, which is based on statistical screening of a wide range of relevant geographic and socio-economic variables.

(A) Final map with nine rurality classes based on Economic Density and Accessibility for each Aggregate Geographic Zone (AGZ) (Alpine, Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean and North) derived from the 13 Environmental Zones of Metzger et al. (2005a,b), (B) Map of the three Rural Typology zones; Peri-Urban, Rural and Deep Rural within the five Aggregate Environmental Zones (AEZ) ; Alpine, Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean and North. (Van Eupen et al., 2012) (Annex 11)

Territories in between

One consequence of the oversimplification of categorisations of territory has been vagueness in the many terms that are used to explain this form of spatial development. Geographers and planners use notions such as suburbanisation, sprawl, urban–rural relations, fringe and peri-urban to try to capture the real diversity and complexity of such territories. Territories in between (TiB) analyzes several industries for research, planning, policy purposes. They have broadened their characterisation beyond population density to examine three main spatial qualities:

- the morphology of mixed built and open spaces;
- the connecting and separating role of infrastructure at different scales; and
- the specific mix of functions at the regional scale.

Territories in between (TiB) determination method based on and CORINE land cover, population density and transport infrastructure (Wandl et al., 2014)

4.2.4 EUROSTAT Territorial classification

EUROSTAT has developed a number of classifications, which are grouped into the following groups: Cluster types, Local typologies, Regional typologies, Other regional typologies (not covered by legislation).

EUROSTAT typologies were developed on the basis of OECD, ESPON and other projects. Unlike in the past, EUROSTAT developed its own approach to defining different areas. EUROSTAT

USES Grid cells, LAU and NUTS 3 levels to define typology criteria. (see Annex 12, 13) Classifications have different legal status and purposes. Cluster types are used to define other areas, Local typologies cover the LAU level, which are municipalities, and serve to bring data closer to places of residence, Regional typologies are based on the NUTS3 level and serve for regional analysis.

Cluster types

1. Cluster types

A functional urban area (FUA) consists of a city and its commuting zone. Functional urban areas therefore consist of a densely inhabited city and a less densely populated commuting zone whose labour market is highly integrated with the city (OECD, 2012). Functional urban areas are a classification based on the following two categories: cities, otherwise referred to as densely populated areas; commuting zones. Cluster types may be identified in relation to the total population living in 1 km² grid cells; The following three types of clusters may be identified:

Urban centre (high-density cluster): a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling;

Urban cluster (moderate-density cluster): a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (including diagonals) with a population density of at least 300 inhabitants per km² and a minimum population of 5 000 inhabitants;

Rural grid cells: grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters. (EUROSTAT, 2018)

This is a functional classification that is not based on territorial division. It is used to define rural areas.

Local typologies

2. Degree of urbanisation (DEGURBA)

The original degree of urbanisation was introduced in 1991 to indicate the character of the area where the respondent lives. Definition was based on the population size and density and contiguity of local administrative units level 2 (LAU2). This typology was derived from the OECD method. The OECD method defines rural regions based on the share of population in rural LAU2s defined based on population density, while the new method is based on grid cells of 1km². (Dijkstra and Poelman, 2014; Eurostat, 2011)

- Densely populated area: (alternate name: cities or large urban area) - At least 50% lives in high-density clusters

- Intermediate density area (alternate name: towns and suburbs or small urban area) - Less than 50% of the population lives in rural grid cells and Less than 50% lives in a high-density cluster
- Thinly populated area (alternate name: rural area) - More than 50% of the population lives in rural grid cells. (EUROSTAT, 2018)

This classification is based on local territorial units, which are often municipalities.

3. Cities, commuting zones and functional urban areas

A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where a majority of the population lives in an urban centre of at least 50 000 inhabitants. A commuting zone contains the surrounding travel-to-work areas of a city where at least 15 % of employed residents are working in the city. A functional urban area consists of a city and its commuting zone. Functional urban areas therefore consist of a densely inhabited city and a less densely populated commuting zone whose labour market is highly integrated with the city (OECD, 2012). Functional urban areas are a classification based on the following two categories: cities, otherwise referred to as densely populated areas; commuting zones. (EUROSTAT, 2018)

4. Coastal areas

Coastal areas are local administrative units (LAUs) that are bordering or close to a coastline. A coastline is defined as the line where land and water surfaces meet (border each other). Coastal areas are a classification based on the following two categories:

Coastal areas: LAUs that border the coastline or LAUs that have at least 50 % of their surface area within a distance of 10 km from the coastline;

Non-coastal areas: LAUs that are not 'coastal areas'; in other words, LAUs that do not border the coastline and have less than 50 % of their surface area within a distance of 10 km from the coastline. (EUROSTAT, 2018)

Regional typologies

5. Urban-rural typology

The urban-rural typology is applied to NUTS level 3 regions: it identifies three types of region based on the share of the rural population. The urban-rural classification is based on data for 1 km² population grid cells, thereby providing more accurate data for the three categories.

The classification was developed by the European Commission based on the OECD approach. The urban-rural typology is a classification based on the following three categories:

- Predominantly urban regions - NUTS 3 regions where at least 80 % of the population live in urban clusters;
- Intermediate regions - NUTS 3 regions where more than 50 % but less than 80 % of the population live in urban clusters;

- Predominantly rural regions - NUTS 3 regions where at least 50 % of the population live in rural grid cells.

6. Metropolitan regions

The metropolitan typology is applied at the level of NUTS level 3 regions and identifies metropolitan regions in the European Union (EU). These regions are defined as urban agglomerations (NUTS level 3 regions or groups of NUTS level 3 regions) where at least 50 % of the population lives inside a functional urban area (FUA) that is composed of at least 250 000 inhabitants.

7. Coastal regions

The coastal typology is applied at the level of NUTS level 3 regions: it identifies coastal regions in the European Union (EU) as having a border with a coastline, having more than half their population within 50 km of the coastline, or having a strong maritime influence.

Other EUROSTAT regional typologies (not covered by legislation):

8. Border regions

9. Island regions

10. Mountain regions

4.2.5 NUTS regions

The Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics or NUTS (French: Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques) has been developed for statistical purposes to ensure a common typology and approach across the EU.

NUTS

NUTS is based on Regulation (EC) No 1059/2003 Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 26 May 2003 on the establishment of a common classification of territorial units for statistics (NUTS)/

European regional statistics are widely used in the context of EU regional policy and to determine eligibility for regions under the cohesion funds.

In order to ensure a harmonised application of the typologies and allow for cross-referencing from other acts and programmes, Eurostat launched a legislative initiative called "Tercet", which is aiming at integrating the typologies into the NUTS Regulation (EUROSTAT, 2018,b).

LAU

To meet the demand for statistics at a local level, Eurostat maintains a system of Local Administrative Units (LAUs) compatible with NUTS. These LAUs are the building blocks of the NUTS, and comprise the municipalities and communes of the European Union.

Since 2017, only one level of LAU has been kept.

The LAUs are: administrative for reasons such as the availability of data and policy implementation capacity; a subdivision of the NUTS 3 regions covering the whole economic territory of the Member States; appropriate for the implementation of local level typologies included in TERCET, namely the coastal area and DEGURBA classification. (EUROSTAT, 2018,c)

5 Track changes in the definition of rural attractiveness

5.1 Development of the concept of rural attractiveness

The direction of changes in the definition of rural attractiveness is based on the following scheme (Figure 5):

Figure 5 Steps of rural attractiveness vision's development

The understanding of rural attractiveness was analysed based on the literature. The original definition was created in D1.1. at the beginning of the project. In D1.1, different contexts of rural attractiveness were analysed. In D1.3, 13 main keywords and 7 rural attractiveness pillars were defined, which were then used to form a needs gathering framework. Pillars was the basis for further developing questionnaires for pilot regions to identify needs and understand aspects of rural attractiveness. It was based on D4.2, D4.4. D1.4 analysed the needs by regions. Based on the literature, it was recognized that the wellbeing and quality of life are inherently multidimensional concepts with a framework encompassing nine dimensions (Eurostat, 2017). Wellbeing and quality of life are the aspects of rural attractiveness that should be considered below.

5.2 The main contexts and factors of rural attractiveness

D1.7 The contexts of rural attractiveness derive from the concept of rural development and regional development. They overlap and complement the initial rural attractiveness contexts discussed in D1.1. It is highlighted by the Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission (Eurostat, 2017) that the wellbeing and quality of life concepts have a framework encompassing nine dimensions. Wellbeing and quality of life can also be seen in this context. Based on the factors of rural attractiveness, and wellbeing formed the seven pillars of rural attractiveness. (Figure 6)

Contexts D1.7	Factors of attractiveness	Wellbeing & quality of life
Growth Process Scale Modernity Theories and approaches Social context Policy context Urban-rural Quality of life Landscapes Rural and agriculture Innovation	Quality of life Territorial capital and rural assets Knowledge and innovations Ecosystem services Multifunctionality of agriculture and farm diversification Social aspects of rural areas Social innovations and innovative activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Material living conditions; 2. Productive or other main activity; 3. Health; 4. Education; 5. Leisure and social interactions; 6. Economic security and personal safety; 7. Governance and basic rights; 8. Natural and living environment; 9. Overall experience of life.
Pillars of attractiveness		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of public and other services 2. Recreation and/or social activities 3. Living conditions, quality of life and standard of living 4. Demographic and human capital 5. Business economy and innovation 6. Social and cultural aspects 7. Environment and biodiversity 		

Figure 6 Contexts factors of attractiveness wellbeing and 7 pillars

Pillars reflect the main factors that determine the attractiveness of the countryside. Further analysis uses direct pillars to determine their significance in pilot areas. The choice of pillars is determined by a set of covered factors, which include quality of life issues, different contexts.

5.3 The current definition of rural attractiveness

An initial vision's definition was performed, which was based on successive steps in the analysis of the literature, searching for rural development contexts, conducting a survey of partner participants, a workshop, during which the initial vision's definition was defined. It was reasonably broad, encompassing various aspects. The following definition of rural attractiveness was chosen by voting in the workshop: *Rural attractiveness is sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment in a working countryside, and an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced*¹.

¹ Scott, A. J., Shorten, J., Owen, R., Owen, I. (2011). What kind of countryside do the public want: community visions from Wales UK?. *GeoJournal*, 76(4), 417-436.

The accepted definition is broad, community based, with an emphasis on agriculture, tourism, accessibility (transport), services, environment. The attractiveness of the countryside in the workshop was defined as follows: Rural attractiveness is about a place where everyone wants to live, enjoys high-quality services, proper infrastructure and community spirit, where jobs and living opportunities abound, and where one can find healthy and resilient environment².

Although the definitions differ, a vision for the future was created - a vision of the attractiveness of the countryside: Rural attractiveness is a place where people want to live because conditions are created for the well-being of people of all ages.

From the definitions discussed in Appendix D1.1 - the definition of rural attractiveness is based on economic benefits, environmental quality, perceptions of the countryside (rural idyll). Attraction is a culture-based concept that cannot unequivocally answer the question of what it is, because it will vary from culture to culture. This is closely related to the needs studied previously (see D1.4, 4.2). The original definition is based on a rural location and a socially accepted understanding of an acceptable living environment. The concept of place is in several definitions related to the community, which is a social place. The initial vision of rural attractiveness includes communities (social environment), sentiment (attitudes based on social and economic characteristics), quality of life - social, environmental and economic characteristics, future perspectives rooted in current trends.

5.4 Categories/ contexts / needs /

D4.2 summarized the needs arising from the pilot SWOT analysis and their prioritization. 32 needs were selected. They were viewed in the following categories (contexts): Quality of life covering Pillar 1: Availability of public and other services and Pillar 3: Living conditions and quality of life; Social capital, which includes Pillar 4: Demographic and human capital and Pillar 5: Business, economy and innovation; Cultural appeal which needs integrated in the Pillar 2: Recreational and social activities and Pillar 6: Social and cultural aspects; Natural capital included in Pillar 7: Environment and biodiversity. (Figure 7)

Figure 7 Categories/contexts of and Pillars of rural attraction in D4.2

Category Quality of life in this sense is understood as the availability of services and living conditions. In the broadest sense, Quality of life includes all capital, assets, and all pillars. These four categories / contexts allow you to look at the pillars related to the diverse needs of pilots. Priority needs were related to pillars and categories / contexts. Of the 32 needs, the needs mentioned for the war pilot were summed up in each pillar. From these needs, the most significant ones were selected, which are the most represented in the particular pillar. The number of pilots who marked this priority need was then looked at. Finally, the needs are related to categories / context. (Table 1)

Pillar	No of needs per pillar	Scarce number of priority needs of pilots	The most important priority according to the number of pilots	Number of pilots for the most important priority	Category/context
1	7	35	Infrastructure and public transport system, connection with urban - rural areas, main cities	11	Quality of life
2	3	14	Leisure and recreation activities for diversified population	6	Cultural appeal
3	6	22	Wellbeing of all inhabitants, enhance quality of life	5	Quality of life
4	4	17	Employment for elderly people	6	Social capital
5	7	32	Transition to Circular economy, bioeconomy, green economy, innovations	8	Social capital
6	2	11	Gender equality	6	Cultural appeal

7	3	15	Adaptation to climate change, low environmental impact	8	Natural capital
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Table 1 The most important needs, pillars and categories

Of these needs, pillars 1 and 5 are the most relevant, related to the Quality of life and Social capital categories respectively. To a lesser extent, this applies to pillars 6 and 2, which are linked to the Cultural appeal. From this it can be concluded that material values, access to services, business are more important. Cultural appeal is little overlooked. From the policy spectrum, the "old" policies related to infrastructure, services, employment, prosperity dominate. "New" policies aimed at new challenges - climate change, transition to circular economy, bioeconomy, green economy, innovations are more characteristic of the 5th and 7th pillars.

In terms of rural attractiveness, there are inequalities between pillars and categories. From the perspective of new policy challenges, Natural and social capital - business and new environment technologies is what is emerging as a major driver of rural areas.

Based on the pilot needs survey, all 9 dimensions of wellbeing and quality of life are covered, but not to the same extent. This is also determined by the limited resources of the project and the different experiences of the partners. Greater attention should be paid to governance issues when analysing pilot needs and policies in particular. There is little emphasis on individual and collective experience.

Pilots have also paid less attention to these issues, both in identifying needs and analysing the policies chosen, as well as in Leisure and social interactions. Emphasis is placed on Productive or other main activities, Material living conditions, Economic security. This does not mean that these dimensions are less important, on the contrary, they are less valued and need more attention in the future.

5.5 Pilots` needs analysis

The needs of pilots are linked to the 7 pillars of rural attractiveness. The methodology provided for needs to be graduated according to priorities. Given the different number of needs in each pilot region, which was not limited (D4.2), in order to be able to compare the proportions, the first 5 needs were selected, assuming that they are the most important (according to the ranking of the regions). Different needs are defined differently and may include one or even more statements that may relate to one or more pillars. The keyword approach was chosen, where the most important keywords were identified from the text. Text analysis was performed to identify the most important and second most important keywords. Next, the first (most important) keyword was used to link needs to the pillars.

Based on the performed analysis, there are significant differences in the different pillars of rural attractiveness. (Figure 8) Compared to the D4.5 analysis, where another method was

used, there is also a marked difference. Overall conclusion - the needs analysis depends on the wording, which allows it to be applied to one or more pillars, because the constant is not known; The grouping of needs depends on the method used to produce the different results. Despite these differences, the total number of needs is Recreational and social activities, which raises the question of whether this factor is important for the attractiveness of rural areas. It may not be relevant in these pilot regions, however, out of 115 needs, the regions have chosen it 3 times. The situation is similar for the 5 priority needs Social and cultural aspects of rural areas, where there are a total of 11 needs related to this pillar.

Undoubtedly, based on the literature review, D1.1 Recreational and social activities and Social and cultural aspects of rural areas are an important factor in the attractiveness of rural areas, which is related to the development of the social environment of the community. What follows from the pilots of the POLIRURAL project is that the existing pilots have developed other priorities as important. Whether this is a general trend should be examined separately.

Figure 8 Amount of pilots needs in according with pillars (5 top priority)

5.6 Pilots` Missions analysis

The pilots formed regional missions, which formed the basis for further needs analysis by creating needs canvas and linking needs to policies (D4.4). Missions provide a general orientation in terms of regional rural attractiveness factors. A text analysis method was used to define by definition the pillars covered by each region's mission. As the formulations often do not have one eligible pillar, an additional one was chosen to characterize the mission of the region. The first is the main, the second is additional. (Figure 9)

Figure 9 Defined pilots` missions by attractiveness pillars

In seven of the 12 pilot regions (first rank), the mission falls under Pillar 5 Business Economy and Innovation. In total, the first and second rank on the 5th pillar is covered by 11 missions. In general, the definitions of missions may not say a clear pillar, however, all or almost all missions refer to business and innovation. Not represented 2. Recreational and social activities; 6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas, which are similar in the needs analysis. (Figure 10, 11)

Number of Pilots missions by attractiveness pillars (first rank)

Figure 10 Number of Pilots missions by attractiveness pillars (first rank)

Figure 11 Number of Pilots missions by attractiveness pillars (second rank)

When compared to the classification of regions used in D4.5 by level of development, then Regions with strong socio-economic growth are more environmental, business and human capital issues, and in contrast, Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale are more likely to belong to 1 pillar Availability of public and other services. Similarly, it can be assumed that environmental and landscape issues are important for densely populated periurban economically developed areas (in our case it is one pilot). However, this does not mean that generalizations are valid here, which can only be confirmed by a more extensive study. The determination of need is influenced by institutions and personal, the result is an agreement based on different interests, knowledge, policy documents, and simply - social experience. It results in differences in seemingly similar areas and common characteristics, in different areas.

Analyzing several deliverables and different approaches to the grouping and selection of needs, the missions defined by the pilots, the overall conclusions are the dominance of Pillar 5 and the weak representation of social and cultural issues (Pillars 2 and 6).

5.7 Typology of pilot territories

The typology of the pilot area is context specific. When analyzing the needs of areas that reflect the attractiveness of the countryside, the rural typology can be seen in the context of the planning process. (Figure 12)

Figure 12 Territorial needs and policy evaluation

Types of rural areas are characteristics of an area that can be understood as a list of needs. In essence, it is a first inventory of needs that takes place in a socially determined and not necessarily political environment. All site classifications are based on numerical data, which allows the site to be characterized and classified according to certain criteria. This is followed by a planning process in which needs are defined based on additional knowledge, involving actors, including policy makers. Finally, the policy assessment forms a selection that focuses on the achievement of site-specific objectives. This is also a political decision, because it analyses a particular policy or what its actions are.

5.7.1 Pilot typologies

Different rural typologies provide an opportunity to get an idea of the characteristics of a rural area, its size (NUTS level, accessibility, economic specialization, connection with cities, level of economic development, other characteristics). It forms the basis for predefined territorial needs. The peculiarity of this project is very different areas. At NUTS level, they cover 4 regions at NUTS 1 level, 3 regions, NUTS 3 - 3 regions and LAU - 1 region. The different scale of the regions limits the possibilities for comparison, but allows us to look at the experiences of different examples. The scale of the policy chosen for the pilot analysis may differ from the NUTS levels of the participating regions. The local level (LAU) has been selected for analysis by 3 regions. (Table 2)

Pilots	NUTS regions	NUTS policy pilots
Flanders	NUTS1	NUTS1
Monaghan	LAU	LAU
Segóbriga/Cuenca	NUTS3	LAU
Vidzeme	NUTS3	NUTS3
Mazowieckie	NUTS2	NUTS2
Central Bohemian Region	NUTS2	NUTS2
Slovakia	NUTS1	NUTS1
Häme	NUTS3	NUTS3
Central Greece	NUTS1	NUTS1
Apulia	NUTS2	NUTS2
Gevgelija-Strumica/ North Macedonia	NUTS1	LAU
Galilee	X	X

Table 2 Regions by NUTS classification

By choosing the level of development used in D4.5 as a basis, we can create rural typological differences for different pilot regions. As an example, let's choose the OECD classification (Figure 13)

Figure 13 Pilot regions by economic development, OECD urban – rural and EDORA structural typology

As can be seen from the figure, both the OECD and EDORA describe different aspects of rural areas, but the correlation between socio-economic development and these rural aspects is strong. For example, a region with strong socio-economic growth is associated with predominantly urban, which is the periurban region, and predominantly rural close to the city, which is consumption countryside. This can be explained by the origin of the typologies discussed in the literature. It should be noted that the typology is developed for the NUTS3 level and NUTS2 or NUTS1 can be several types of regions. Typologies have been developed for different purposes and their use has different meanings. These typologies are not regulated by EU regulations and serve as an analysis tool or reference. Pilot regions outside the EU are not included here, as they are not included in the EDORA, OECD classifications considered. For other typologies, see Annex 14.

In the context of rural attractiveness, a region with strong socio-economic growth (2) is more associated with the urban environment and urban consumption, both as an agricultural product and as a landscape, tourism and residence. Regions with moderate socio-economic growth (2) are characterized by an average situation between urban and rural with different characteristics. Although the territories depend on the cities, there are also differences in the economic structure, which depend on the specifics of the region. For example, in sparsely populated areas, the features of agriculture and peripherality are increasing. Proximity to major urban centers allows for economic benefits. Regions with growth on a smaller scale (6) is the most diverse group and covers different cases of location, population density, urban-rural relations. Depending on historical circumstances, suburban regions that cover capitals may also have different economic specializations and, consequently, different understandings of rural attractiveness.

5.7.2 Pilots of socio-economic differences clusters

The regional clustering method was used in D1.4 to determine socio-economic differences. For comparison of pilot regions, 24 territorial development indicators were chosen and further analyzed. Of which: Basic statistics, Agriculture, Share of population (from 25 to 64 years) by education level, Share of economic activity NACE R2 from total GVA. Comparing with the EUROSTAT classification, it was concluded that only a few regions (Cuenca, Vidzeme and Galilee) are eligible for rural designation. The conclusion is based on the economic approach where the main criterion was chosen - Share of economic activity NACE R2 from total GVA, to the exclusion of Monaghan, Central Greece, where other sectors predominate. Pilot regions' sizes and degree of urbanization were used for cluster analysis. According to geographical location, Mediterranean countries, the second one - Central European countries, the third cluster Northern countries are divided. (Table 3)

Pilots	Geographical clusters D1.4	Development clusters D1.4	Survey clusters D1.4	Development clusters D4.5
Flanders	Central European	3	3	Regions with strong socio-economic growth
Monaghan	Northern	2	1	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Segóbriga/Cuenca	Mediterranean	1	2	Regions with moderate socio-economic growth
Vidzeme	Northern	1	6	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Mazowieckie	Central European	1	3	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Central Bohemian Region	Central European	3	3	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Slovakia	Central European	2	6	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Häme	Northern	1	4	Regions with strong socio-economic growth
Central Greece	Mediterranean	2	5	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale

Apulia	Mediterranean	1	5	Regions with moderate socio-economic growth
Gevgelija-Strumica/ North Macedonia	Mediterranean	1	2	Non-EU pilots
Galilee	Mediterranean	?	4	Non-EU pilots

Table 3 Region Clusters of D1.4

According to the development criteria, 3 clusters have been distinguished. Cluster 1 includes Apulia, Cuenca, North Macedonia, Mazowieckie, Hame and Vidzeme; Cluster 2 includes Central Greece, Slovakia and Monaghan; Cluster 3 - Central Bohemia and Flanders. D4.5 defines rural typology based on development indicators. There are 4 clusters: Regions with strong socio-economic growth, Regions with moderate socio-economic growth, Regions with socio-economic growth on a smaller scale, Non-EU pilot. This classification differs from the level of development classification used in D1.4. This can be explained by the differences in the selected indicators, the purpose of creation. D4.5 Regional differences are designed to analyze the link between policy impact and level of development. D1.4 - the aim is to form a basis for assessing regional differences in the attractiveness of rural areas.

5.7.3 Pilot rural area attractiveness factor survey clusters

D1.4 grouping of similarities of answers by regions and grouping of similarities of answers in clusters was performed. The regions were grouped into 6 clusters according to the similarity of the survey answers. It was concluded that the answers are based on the region's development state. Survey responses of less developed — North Macedonia, Cuenca, Galilee, Apulia, Central Greece, Latvia and Slovakia — belong to the first cluster; the second cluster includes responses from Mazowieckie, Hame and Apulia. The larger and most developed regions' responses are in the third cluster.

In addition, in D1.4, the similarity of the questionnaire answers was grouped, where 3 groups were determined by the similarity of the answers (positive versus negative answers). The first group included a set of answers defined by rural rurality, that is, the characteristics of the region. The second group is the answers, which are common to all regions. The third group describes regional disparities. This grouping was not related to the regional context. Previous clustering of regions does not provide a clear answer to the question of the contexts of rural attractiveness, but only highlights regional differences.

By choosing different goals and applying different methods, different typologies (clusters) are obtained. Often such differences cannot be explained without knowing a specific approach or method.

6 Pilots` policy analysis

6.1 Policy analysis

Conclusions from the pilot analysis were performed within the framework of T4.5 Evaluation Of Regional Policy Measures. The policy choice was based on the needs of the regions, the link with the objectives of each region's activities, as well as linking it to the pillars of rural attractiveness. (Table 4)

Pilots	Policy	Policy scale/ level by deliver	Policy Scale/ level by pilot analysis	Development specification	Aims/ clarification	Effectiveness	Relevance	Coherence	Policy justification
Flanders	Rural development programme Flanders 2014-2020 RDP III Agri-Environmental-climate management Agreements (AEA)	national	national	rural development	Rural development, focus on ecosystems, climate, focus on natural resources	Not explained	Not explained	Not explained	regional needs, rural characteristics
Monaghan	Monaghan LEADER Local Development Strategy – Actions under Environmental Theme (2014-2020)	national	local	rural development	New entrants, Economic Development, Enterprise, Development and Job Creation, Social Inclusion, Rural Environment	moderate/high	moderate/high	moderate/high	entrants, needs,
Segóbriga	The measure to be evaluated is Sub-measure 19.2 within the LEADER measure of the PDR (Rural Development Program) of the Castilla-La Mancha, implemented by the Local Action Group (LAG) ADESIMAN	regional	local	rural development	Innovation, diversification, public infrastructure, services	moderate/high	High	High EU, moderate in lower level	needs, influence to territory
Vidzeme	LEADER measure 19.21 - as part of Rural Development program 2014-2020	national	regional	rural development	Diversification, economic activities, employment	high	moderate	High EU, low in National level	needs, multisectorality, planned to period 2020-2027, implemented in region, entrepreneurship, involvement

									of region stakeholders
Vidzeme	"Specific Objective No. 3.3.1. "To increase private investments in regions, by making investments for entrepreneurship development according to economic specialization of territories stated in development programmes of municipalities and based on needs of local entrepreneurs" of the Operational Program "Growth and Employment" 2014-2020	national	regional	regional development	Road infrastructure, investments in business	high	moderate	Low in national level	needs, multisectorality, planned to period 2020-2027, implemented in region, entrepreneurship, involvement of region stakeholders
Mazowieckie	Local: described in Local Development Strategy of LAG	regional	local	rural development	Entrepreneurship	moderate	High	Exists national, level in EU	new entrants, business development, needs
Central Bohemian Region	the Development strategy of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2018-2024	regional	regional	regional development	Economic Development, Research and Development, Tourism, Human Capital and Education, Transport, Energy Infrastructure, Environment, ICT Infrastructure, Social and Health Services and Culture	moderate/low	high/contradictory	high	needs, regional development, sustainability, resilience, technologies, innovation
Slovakia	Implementation of the EU Quality Policy in Slovakia	national	national	rural development	Competitiveness of the Slovak agro-food products	low	low	low	EU Quality Policy in Slovakia, SK competitiveness
Häme	LOCAL TIME - Hämeenlinna region's local development strategy for 2014-2020.	national	local	rural development	Business, services, circular economy, well-being, employment	high	high	moderate, unclear	Business, needs, Future Relevance, Policy Influence, Easy access to required

	Leader Group Linnaseutu ry								information , Implementati on Status.
Central Greece	LEADER-Rural Development Programme (RDP) 2007– 2013:	regional	local	rural development	Competitive ness of local companies, diversificati on of the rural economy, quality of life, services	hight	hight	hight	vision and the main needs, Increase of population , Support of start-up business , Increase initiatives and organized actions
Apulia	RDP 2014-2020 Apulia program implementatio n, M19	regional	regional	rural development	All M19 - tasks preparation startegies, implementa tion, cooperation , support LAGs	moderate/low	moderate/lo w	moderate/low	needs, attractiveness pillars,
Gevgelija- Strumica	Annual Program for Financial Support for Rural Development (2019) Measure 124 - Investments in infrastructure for development of agriculture, forestry and water and economy	national	national	rural development	Infrastructur e, living conditions, economic activities	hight	hight/modera te	hight	swot, needs analysis, data availability, infrastructure
Galilee	The National Digital Program of the Government of Israel	national	local	regional development	Tourism, agriculture, digitalizatio n infrastructure, innovation, start-up, entrepreneu rs, young people	Not explained	Not explained	Not explained	New needs, entartnts, tourism, education, digitalization, transport

Table 4 Policy evaluation pilots

What policies were chosen?

All the selected policy measures address needs in the area of pillar 5: economic activity and innovation. Seven of the policy measures have shown needs related to Pillar 1: Availability of public and other services. Five also address needs related to pillar 7: Environment and biodiversity. Four with pillar 3: Living conditions and quality of life and pillar 4: Demographics and Human capital and two with pillar 6: Social and cultural aspects of rural areas.

LEADER has chosen to analyse 7 pilots out of 12. This shows the widespread interest of the place-based approach in the regions. LEADER as a basis for policy analysis emphasizes its role in promoting rural development, high efficiency. LEADER addresses local issues that are not

funded by other instruments, so it is important in the context of the CAP and rural development.

The analysis of other policies has been chosen by 6 pilot regions. The coverage of these sectors is very different, mostly related to national level programs. The pilots analyse landscape policy, regional policy of socio-economic development, business promotion, development measures of certain sectors at the national level.

What were the conditions for policy choices?

Limitations on the choice to be analysed: The choice was not so much related to whether it was relevant to the region, but to other selection factors. (including data availability, implementation progress). This does not make it possible to unambiguously link the policies under analysis to needs and further to the attractiveness of the countryside. For the selection of the policy measure, the following criteria shall be taken into account:

- Future Relevance: the policy responds to one or more critical or relevant needs
- Policy Influence: Capacity to steer and monitor policy measures in this area
- Easy access to required information
- Implementation Status: The policy measure must be completed or in an advanced stage of implementation (80%). It must be ensured that there will be enough information available (qualitative and quantitative) to evaluate it.

How was this justified?

In the case of LEADER, if the whole measure 19 is analysed, then the affiliation to the pillars is not so unambiguous, because the measure includes support for various different activities. Often the descriptions of needs and rationale do not give an unambiguous answer and there may be different interpretations during the extension process.

The choice of policy analysis was determined in accordance with the methodology developed by POLIRURAL. At the same time, the pilots also took into account other criteria. The most common was compliance with the priorities mentioned by 11 of the 12 pilots. In addition, the following were used: regional characteristics, business and entrepreneurial development, regional development, entrants, influence to territory, multisectorality, implemented in region, involvement of regional stakeholders, sustainability, resilience, technologies, innovation, competitiveness, Increase of population, tourism, education, digitalization, transport. Part of them corresponds either to the priorities selected during the project or to the priorities set out in the regional policy documents.

When choosing a policy for evaluation, the regions did not always take into account the importance of the policy in relation to its ranking, which was also not required by the methodology. Therefore, the importance of the chosen policy in relation to the priorities cannot be assessed unambiguously.

Almost all pilots have chosen a policy that is related to priorities in one way or another. However, the importance of policy varies. (Table 5)

Pilots	The top need rank covered by policy	Total needs covered by policy	Top need pillar	The top need rank by pillar
Flanders	1	3	5	5
Monaghan	1	6	4	4
Segóbriga	1	5	4	4
Vidzeme	1	2	6	6
Mazowieckie	8	4	3	5
Central Bohemian Region	1	7	1	1
Slovakia	0	0	5	0
Häme	1	5	5	5
Central Greece	1	2	4	4
Apulia	1	3	5	5
Gevgelija-Strumica	6	1	5	1
Galilee	1	9	5	5

Table 5 The link of the chosen policy to the highest rank of needs, number of eligible needs and pillar

Nine of the 12 pilots selected pilots for analysis, which is the No. 1 priority. , three pilots have chosen policies that are not at the top of the needs priorities. The total number of policy priorities also depends on the number of needs, which varies from pilot to pilot. The link between the selected policies and the attractiveness pillar shows that the highest priority needs are six for Pillar 5, three for Pillar 4, and one for Pillar 1, 3 and 6. At the same time, the ranking of the priorities of the chosen policy needs in five refers to Pillar 5, three to Pillar 4, two to Pillar 1, one to Pillar 6.

In terms of rural attractiveness, the link between the policies chosen reflects the overall dominance of Pillar 5, which is Business Economy and Innovation. In the case of some pilots, it is not easy to determine the relevance of the chosen policy to one of the needs and, consequently, to the pillars of rural attractiveness.

At what level / scale?

Method - how to determine effectiveness, relevance, and coherence is unclear. This uncertainty is increased by the available data of each selected policy document or action to be analysed, the approach used, the specifics of the policy itself, including the scale of the chosen policy (local, regional, national).

Pilot regions have chosen different levels of policy for evaluation. Policy makers are at national and regional level, policy makers at national, regional and local level. Several regions have opted for a lower level of policy analysis, which is local or regional. In the case of LEADER, the policy is evaluated at the following sub-levels: National, regional, local, including LAG, LAG level.

How do policies relate to rural development and regional development?

Most of the pilots have chosen a rural development policy for evaluation. This applies to measures that are LEADER, agri-environment. These policies are part of the CAP and as such are part of the EU's rural policy. However, the broad scope of LEADER goes beyond rural development issues and is partly related to regional development. Regional development is linked to policies that do not specifically target the countryside (for example, promoting development in general or business). Here it is difficult to separate from rural development if the focus is on the countryside and then there is an overlap between rural and regional development.

“Top-down” versus “bottom-up”

The EU's single requirements and regulatory approach to LEADER may have been instrumental in extending the scope of this instrument, but has influenced a place-based approach that is becoming top-down, with less space-based consideration for specific needs. This is indicated by the evaluations of some pilots and publications on LEADER.

Most of the other policies chosen do not involve a bottom-up approach, as it is implemented at national or regional level. A more space-blind approach is typical. The place here is not so much respected. Some pilots have indicated that local communities are not consulted and that the needs of local regions are not taken into account. However, as the cases are very different, the same cannot be said for all pilots. It is mentioned that local governments have been consulted in planning and coordinating projects. Although in this case it is a national policy, local interests are respected.

Of all pilot cases (13 policies evaluated in total), 8 apply to the bottom-up and 5 to the space-blind.

What sectors was the policy analysis focused on?

Most of the pilots cover different sectors of the economy. This is especially true for LEADER activities. This suggests that the policies chosen are in line with the understanding of rural development as a multidimensional policy with less emphasis on agriculture. Agriculture is also ambiguous, as it includes contexts such as climate, business, landscape, which expands the coverage of sectors. On the other hand, different sectors specific to LEADER policies are assessed with different emphases, where in one case it may be more focused on agriculture, elsewhere on food production, services or wider diversification.

LEADER covers a wide range of economic sectors and their development depends on other policies, such as demography, employment, social assistance, taxation, regulation, regional policy in general, external crises such as economic or COVID, which are mentioned in the pilot analysis.

What were the policy objectives?

The policy objectives analysed reflect the diversity of policies and the needs of pilots. In general, more emphasis is placed on economic development issues. Here are some examples of keywords: competitiveness of local companies, diversification of the rural economy, quality of life, services, well-being, employment, living conditions, tourism, agriculture, digitalization, innovation, start-up, entrepreneurs, young people, road infrastructure, investments in business, public infrastructure, new entrants, social inclusion, rural environment, ecosystems, climate changes, natural resources.

It is not possible to list quantitative objectives because they have been described by pilots in different ways and at different levels of detail. It depends on the policies chosen by the pilots, which are very different.

What were the shortcomings in the implementation of the policies?

The pilot region points to limitations, obstacles to policy implementation. In the case of LEADER, communication with beneficiaries is important, which influences attitudes towards policy evaluation.

LEADER pilot policy evaluations assess it as an effective, relevant and coherent policy. This is also confirmed by the pilot cases. Despite the positive assessment, there are a number of cases that demonstrate the effectiveness of policy implementation, such as pre-financing difficulties, changing tax and regulatory conditions, late start program, routine work, problems with community involvement. Problems related to the program coherence are mentioned: organization and coordination with the various stakeholders' procedures, co-operations knowledge transfer between offices and advisors, poor coordination, delay in the implementation of projects.

Relevance is mostly noted as meeting local needs, but it is mentioned that there is a lack of sustainability, there is uncertainty about the future. Pilots note the need to continue the policy.

In general, other (except LEADER) policies have different assessments of policy impact. Weaknesses include co-financing problems, lack of knowledge, cooperation issues, the impact of COVID, uncertainty about the future, program delays, planning issues, regulatory problems, which are generally similar to the LEADER cases mentioned above.

Recommendations for the definition of rural attractiveness.

An important factor is the capacity of institutions, the role of leaders who have the knowledge, ability to guide and implement goals. Given the importance of services, public services are a factor that is less seen, but which affects the attractiveness of rural areas. The COVID framework and external factors have had different effects on policy implementation. The causes are not unambiguous. In our opinion, the explanations may be related to the different policy activities that affect different sectors, the scale of policy implementation.

What was the impact (effectiveness, relevance, coherence)?

According to the applied POLIRURAL policy evaluation methodology, the pilots evaluated the developed policy based on data - both quantitative and qualitative. Surveys, interviews, expert opinions, a text mining tool, and available quantitative data were used to assess the impact of the policy. According to the methodology, the policy measure Effectiveness, Relevance, Coherence was assessed by answering the following questions:

Effectiveness of the policy measures

To what extent the policy measure has achieved its objectives? Includes an evidence-based judgement of the progress made.

- What were the key success factors in achieving the objectives?
- What were the key obstacles hindering the progress?

Relevance of the policy measures

- To what extent the objectives of the policy measure met the initial needs?
- How well do the original objectives correspond to the current needs?
- To what extent the policy measure is still relevant?

Coherence of the policy measures

- To what extent is the policy measure coherent with other policy interventions having similar objectives?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other local and regional policy measures?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant national policy measures?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant EU policy measures? E.g. CAP, LEADER, digital transformation, green deal, demographic change, etc.
- To what extent the policy measure is contributing to EU added value? (e.g. EU Regional Targets: Globalisation, climate change, energy challenge, demographic change)

Due to the different regions, the choice of different policies in terms of scale, timing, sectors or areas covered, scope of measures to be assessed, it is difficult to compare the effects of the policy. There are cases where the policy is already in place for 2007-2013. and is currently being implemented, where impacts are expected after 2023. The different experience of pilot regions in policy analysis, different methods used must be taken into account. Most of the pilots assessed the impact based on stakeholder surveys. Little use was made of an expert, independent approach that could provide additional input to the evaluation.

Most pilots used gradation moderate-high to describe the effect. Some pilots did not explain the gradation and rationale for the impact of the policy. Relevance to needs and the link between the policy and other policies were noted. However, a high factor of subjectivity must be taken into account here, which may influence such an assessment. More impact may be shown by the challenges arising from the block of effectiveness issues. This is where the question of whether a policy has been adequately assessed appears. The second factor is a

comparison of initial and final needs, which raises the question of the permanence of the policy or the achievement of objectives.

7 Conclusions

7.1 Conclusions from literature review

The attractiveness of rural areas through rural development concepts takes on a contextual perspective that allows it to be linked to targeted actions and change processes

Rural development, regional development is considered in the context of the development concept.

Rural development, regional development are social constructs that are unclear, variable in time and space

Development understand in general terms as a process of change, on the one hand, and policy intervention, on the other

Development has many connotations - growth, modernity, cultural context, politics, scale, etc.

Rural development, regional development covers territorial change processes and policies.

Rural development is viewed in the context of urban-rural and rural-agricultural dualism

Rural development depends on understanding rural areas.

Rurality is an ambiguous concept that changes over time and over territories.

Rural development is not more understand as growth and agriculture

The paradigm of rural development growth is currently largely dominant

Although the coverage and understanding of rural policy is changing, the role of agriculture as a pivot policy in rural development is still present.

The relationship between urban and rural areas is not one-way, complex and multidimensional

Rural development is associated with neo-endogenous development, quality of life, attractiveness.

The policy and intervention perspective provides an insight into the countryside and rural development

Rural development, regional development are interconnected and overlapping, but not identical concepts

Regional development, unlike Rural development, is understood more as a political process that creates change.

Regional development as a political process is understood as the reduction of differences between territories

Regional development traditionally been more focused on the economic development component

Various regional policy models - place-based and space-blind - still exist and are being implemented

Location-oriented development in the case of LEADER is controversial.

Regional development is increasingly important for the cultural context, cooperation of personnel and institutions (behavioural economics), territorial cultural differences.

Personal motivation and institutional capacity play an important role in rural development processes.

The typologies of rural areas based on the OECD, modifying them and supplementing them according to various objectives.

Typologies developed in the projects are of a methodological nature that can be used in the future.

The classification of rural-urban areas is moving from the density and population criterion in the area to a functional view of the areas (FUA)

Classification of rural-urban areas. In addition to territorial statistics of various scales, other sources are increasingly used, especially LANDCOVER, 1 km grid data, GIS processing capabilities.

There are challenges in integrating administrative, functional data in changing circumstances that modify the view on rural areas

7.2 Factors that determine rural attractiveness

The study analysed the factors of rural attractiveness in their interrelation. The original definition is broad enough and does not require revision. However, taking into account the analysed literature, rural attractiveness factors / contexts, certain aspects should be emphasized. The initial contexts / factors analysed in previous studies should be complemented by a number of contexts.

The determinants of the definition of rural attractiveness are rooted, on the one hand, in our understanding of the countryside and attractiveness, on the other hand, in the set of contexts that are included in this understanding to characterize it. This set of contexts is usually emphasized more than the understanding of the concept itself. Both are interconnected and semantically dependent. The concepts are explained in contexts. In turn, the choice of contexts is in terms of researchers, socially determined environment, policy or other circumstances. As a result, we gain different understandings over time and place. Policy

responses to needs create new concepts that complement or incorporate old ones by transforming them.

Over time, the very concept of the countryside has changed, adding a multidimensional view of spatial relationships.

Changes in the definition of rural attractiveness would be related to policy choices, culture, regional differences.

Taking into account the determinants of rural attractiveness D1.1 and the analysis of the D1.7 literature, the most important thing is the personal perception, which is realized through policy goals. It is this cut that allows the connection of rural attractiveness, actors and actions that are stakeholders motivated. Directly motivated personal perception, which is based on personal needs and is transmitted through social institutions and processes in defining the needs of territories, allows to raise the question of the accents of the definition of rural attractiveness.

The recommendation in defining the attractiveness of rural areas is related to an active process promoting rural development, which is rooted in the sustainability of quality of life and is motivated by all participants. Factors (needs) characterizing the quality of life are agreed on the basis of maximum involvement of community members.

The level of development of regions may not be related to the attractiveness of rural areas. Probably, it is rather determined by the location of the region near urban areas (location, accessibility factors), cultural differences, the historical structure of the farm and other conditions. The cultural context and the level of economic development of each region determine the set of values that the regions view differently, forming different views on the needs of the territories.

The practice of having the same measures throughout the EU, the same regulation giving the same effects to different territories, is not scientifically justified. Policies must be place-respecting, whether it is a bottom-up or a top-down approach.

The over-orientation of infrastructure needs criticized in the literature only shows the need for such an approach, as regions live in different time reference systems - original EU countries, new member states, pre-accession situation, post-socialist countries, etc., which create different space and require different policies.

The understanding of rural attractiveness is scale-oriented. At the local level, it is more related to the emotional component, the human factor, the group of people, and the views of the community. People make decisions about living in the countryside based on social, economic and local considerations. At the regional level, attractiveness becomes more of an economic indicator, a set of characteristics that becomes less emotional, more formalized.

The community, the ability to communicate, to shape their own activities based on local needs play an important role in promoting the attractiveness of rural areas. This is particularly the

case for LEADER and solid local initiatives. It is important to address issues of mutual coordination between institutions. The capacity of institutions is important, knowledge that should be improved. Given the importance of services, public services are a factor that is less seen, but which affects the attractiveness of rural areas. Coherence with other policies should be improved, both at different policy levels and between policies.

Top-down policies related to regional development issues need to consult more with local beneficiaries, who are often local governments, entrepreneurs, farmers. These issues cannot be unambiguously regulated and it depends on the peculiarities of culture, level of knowledge, acceptance of innovations. Here it is important to create an exchange of experience, educational activities that are expected within the framework of policies.

Based on the findings of behaviour economics, an important factor is the capacity of institutions, the role of leaders who have the knowledge, ability to guide and implement goals. It also corresponds to the quality of life and wellbeing perceptions.

Analysing the factors that make up the attractiveness of rural areas, we found that there are inequalities between the seven pillars and categories. This is complemented by a link between needs. Business, economy and innovation and Availability of public and other services play a key role, while social and cultural contexts are less valued (pillars 2, 6). This can be explained by the dominance of the economic view in development issues in general, and the view of specific needs in the pilot areas.

From the perspective of new policy challenges, Natural and social capital - business and new environment technologies is what is emerging as a major driver of rural areas. This is indicated by the selected needs of the pilots (pillars 5 and 7) and justified by the Rural policy 3.0.

In general, rural attractiveness pillars adequately characterize both the quality of life and wellbeing, and the required understanding of coverage. Further development of the understanding of the attractiveness of rural areas can be complemented by the factors discussed above, but it should be borne in mind that there will be territorial differences.

As rural areas are different, requiring different approaches to addressing needs, detailing the factors is a task for each rural community.

There is the question of the dualism of the definition of rural attractiveness - as a social or political concept. It can be said that it covers both. As social it includes various factors / contexts, how one can look at the attractiveness of the countryside. As a political one, it depends on a decision that is important for the attractiveness of the countryside. Both are based on the cultural context of the place. This is due, for example, to selected priorities and needs that are politically motivated.

If the attractiveness of the countryside has an emotional context, there is the question of what constitutes this emotion and how it contrasts with rational, including politically motivated, thinking. How much rural attractiveness in general is emotional and how much political context. The pilots' analysis shows a dual shift in the political direction.

7.3 Conclusions on policy implications

There is a dilemma in policy evaluations. The assessment compares the relevance at the outset of the policy with the expected need for the policy in the future, to which most pilots have replied that the policy is relevant at the outset, now and in the future. When defining policy objectives, there may not be a clear need value to be achieved. In policy, the results are viewed in relation to the stated goal of the policy, which may be insufficient in terms of the amount of needs that could be addressed. The policy has been right, the targets are being met, but the investment is insufficient to say that the need has been met. There are several interpretations here: - does the fact that the need and the policy are appropriate in the future mean that the need has not changed over the course of the policy (the need for a change of time); that the policy did not work and that the need is therefore urgent; it will continue to be relevant in the future, regardless of the objectives achieved, as the need is permanent and covers a longer period than one policy cycle.

The project did not have enough resources and time to provide a detailed assessment of the impact of the policy, so the pilots relied on the numerical values achieved, which may not reveal the magnitude of the impact.

Assessing the pilot regions by the level of economic development in clusters, relevance is a larger pilot with strong economic growth. However, clustering covering 12 regions may not always be indicative of the trend as a whole, as the 2 participants in the cluster may not be representative to draw further conclusions. In this case, the organization of the evaluation process, the selected interview and survey participants, which differ from pilot region to region, may also have an impact. This is indicated by the responses on effectiveness and implementation weaknesses, which coincide with the literature review on the role of social factors in promoting development and also in policy evaluation.

8 Recommendations

The following directions are based on this study - literature review and pilot needs.

8.1 Areas that can be explored in future research

The cultural context should be emphasized. Experience, type of economic activity, natural and historical conditions determine a great diversity, which has an impact on our thinking and actions, including decision-making, institution-building, selection of key actors.

The socio-economic basis of development should be further studied, because development is determined by employment, human resources (capital), economic structure, available resources, including financial, natural, human, etc. The sum and interaction of different factors form different environments for development.

Persistence of development trends, which characterize not only the current situation or changes at some time, but also, the speed of these changes, analysis of causes, persistence, permanence. This is especially true of quality of life characteristics.

Orientation from a sectoral approach to a territorial one - how sectoral policies can and do affect rural areas, specific places. At present, there is still little research in this context.

Research at different scales - how attractiveness is related to location - and the scale of places. D1.7 looks at the attractiveness of rural areas at EU level. The pilot's contribution is regional in scope. The Deep Diving approach could complement this multidimensional view in this context.

Personal and institutional links in shaping local needs and defining policies are a direction that has received little attention in research. The field of personal leadership resonates with place-based, bottom-up approaches that characterize new approaches to rural development.

Given the importance of services, public services are a factor that is less seen, but which affects the attractiveness of rural areas. Strong state and municipal institutions, leadership, quality of services, form the identity of territories, attitudes that are part of the attractiveness of the countryside.

The social environment in the countryside (community) is under-represented in the needs of pilots. What follows from the pilots of the POLIRURAL project is that the existing pilots have chosen other priorities as important. Whether this is a general trend should be examined separately.

Attention should be paid to innovation and its territorial dimension, as innovation is the driving force behind rural development. This is especially true for social innovations, which are less studied.

Methodological aspects of evaluation are important in policy evaluation - how the methodology affects the evaluation, what methods are used, how adequate they are, how judgments are formed, etc. questions are essential to answer the evaluation questions.

As development is no longer clearly linked to growth, the factors that determine rural development in the place of growth should be considered, for example, in the context of shrinking and development.

8.2 Recommendations for policy

The initial analysis of rural attractiveness focused in part on agricultural and rural attractiveness factors related to agriculture, such as new entrants, multifunctionality, ecosystem services, capitals and assets. Given the contexts of rural and regional development, the emphasis should be on rural development rather than agriculture, creating a balance of approaches. The countryside cannot be part of agricultural policy, on the contrary, rural policy includes agriculture.

Rural development must be linked to the coordination of the various funds, funds and institutions responsible. A mechanism needs to be put in place to look at rural development more broadly.

Policies of Covid, Climate change, CAP - three big pillars that should be complemented by place-based policies, responding at different harmonized levels of government.

Digitization of rural areas, support for innovation and knowledge, together with the social environment of communities form the basis for changes in the attractiveness of rural areas.

The role and motivation of leadership should be strengthened as an important factor in the development of rural areas.

Policies need to take into account the different aspects of rural attractiveness and reconcile social, business and environmental issues.

Policies need to build complementary links at different levels / scales and in different approaches (bottom-up, top down; space blind; place based; endogenous, exogenous development), taking into account the different needs of rural areas, cultural contexts, places.

The development of bottom-up policies, such as LEADER, smart villages, should allow for action based on local needs, with effective inter-institutional coordination.

At a lower level, more effective cooperation between policy makers, implementers and local / regional authorities should be supported and promoted.

Factors of rural attractiveness that are less valued - Social environment in rural areas - should be supported.

8.3 Recommendations for practice

For the evaluation of the policy, it is necessary to develop more detailed methodological explanations, taking into account the different experiences of the participants and possible different understandings of the issues.

It would be important to agree on the link between the policy selection under analysis and the top priorities defined by the pilot region.

Coherence - Although many have indicated in the evaluation that policies are well linked to others, there are no linkage criteria that do not allow for unequivocal coherence.

Analysing 12 different pilots with it is not enough to form clusters and to judge their connection with needs, typical regional characteristics, regional rural attractiveness factors or specific policies. There must be a larger group or typical representative cases.

As an alternative to possible typical cases of deep dives, based on local needs Top priorities.

The policy implementation process itself is important. Important here are the participants in the process, who are involved, what questions are asked, who summarizes the results, who

decides on the amount of knowledge in decision-making. This should be taken into account when selecting participants.

To encourage new acceptance, it is important to change thinking. This should be done in knowledge and action motivating activities.

When developing regional strategies, various aspects of rural attractiveness should be taken into account, which can increase the applicability of the policy in rural development.

8.4 Further clarification of the concept of rural attractiveness

The study does not provide a specific new definition of rural attractiveness. Nor has it been a task. The study analysed Track and present changes in the definition of rural attractiveness, Factors that determine rural attractiveness, and provided recommendations for further research, policy, and practice.

The definition of track changes of rural attractiveness indicates that the initial understanding of rural attractiveness has basically been correct and should be maintained. Several contexts have changed over time. 7 pillars of attractiveness were defined, 9 dimensions of wellbeing & quality of life, sustainability was recognized as critical for rural development. This study looked at the concepts of rural development and regional development in different contexts that complement existing factors; differences between pilot regions in terms of rural attractiveness factors. More emphasis was placed on linking policies to rural attractiveness factors. Finally, the initial emphasis on agriculture was complemented by a broader view of rural development, emphasizing the importance of the place, the complexity of the policy, the social and cultural factors.

The factors that determine rural attractiveness are perceived as a set of contexts in which we view the complexity of the area. When analysing pilot regions, these factors were considered in relation to pilot needs, chosen policies, objectives, policy impacts, scales, territorial classification (territorial differences), policy approaches, etc. These contexts provided a broader picture of the link between defining rural attractiveness and the policy process. It is the definition, implementation and evaluation of the policy that reveals the regions' views on the attractiveness of rural areas. It was found that Attractiveness factors are not equally important for the whole and for individual regions. It is determined by regional differences, which are reflected in different needs and result in policies.

Recommendations for further research, policy and practice are based on literature studies and analysis of pilot regions. The further use of rural attractiveness in policy-making depends on pilot understanding and acceptance. Feedback from WP5, WP6 could answer the question of how rural attractiveness is used, how it has been useful in achieving pilot objectives.

Acknowledgements

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Annex 1 Development approaches

<i>Decade</i>	<i>Main development approaches</i>
1950s	Modernization theories: all countries should follow the European model Structuralist theories: Southern countries needed to limit interaction with the global economy to allow for domestic economic growth
1960s	Modernization theories Dependency theories: Southern countries poor because of exploitation by Northern countries
1970s	Dependency theories Basic needs approaches: focus of government and aid policies should be on providing for the basic needs of the world's poorest people Neo-Malthusian theories: need to control economic growth, resource use and population growth to avoid economic and ecological disaster Women and development: recognition of the ways in which development has differential effects on women and men
1980s	Neoliberalism: focus on the market. Governments should retreat from direct involvement in economic activities Grassroots approaches: importance of considering local context and indigenous knowledge Sustainable development: need to balance needs of current generation against environmental and other concerns of future populations Gender and development: greater awareness of the ways in which gender is implicated in development
1990s	Neoliberalism Post-development: ideas about 'development' represent a form of colonialism and Eurocentrism. Should be challenged from the grassroots Sustainable development Culture and development: increased awareness of how different social and cultural groups affected by development processes
2000s	Neoliberalism: increased engagement with concepts of globalization Sustainable development Post-development Grassroots approaches Rights-based development

Source: (Willis, 2011)

Annex 2 Development theories and approaches

Name	Main actors	Scale	Definition of development	Description
Classical economic theory	Private sector (the market)	National	Economic growth	Focus on market forces as the most efficient way of organizing economies
Classical Marxism	State	National	Economic growth, industrialization, urbanization, increased complexity of societies	State as key actor in organizing resource distribution and use
Keynesianism	State and market	National	Economic growth, in particular full employment	State intervention in the economy to help regions and groups that are disadvantaged
Modernization theory	State and market	National	Economic growth and increased complexity in social and economic organization	Eurocentric assumptions that all countries should follow the path of Northern nations
Structural approaches	State	National	Economic growth	National governments need to protect domestic production from global markets and competition because of global economic inequalities
Dependency theories	State	National	Economic growth	Economic disadvantage in the global periphery is a result of exploitation from the North; need to withdraw from global economic system
Neoliberalism	Private sector, NGOs and individuals	National and sub-national	Economic growth, liberal democracy	State involvement regarded as being detrimental to development; state should provide regulatory framework within which companies and NGOs can operate
Sustainable development	Depends on perspective	Depends on perspective	Protection of the natural environment	Diversity of approaches to sustainable development; some are very market-led and involve pricing nature, while others involve putting environmental protection at the heart of policy and reducing consumption
Ethnodevelopment	State and ethnic groups	National and sub-national	Recognition of ethnic diversity. Definitions may vary by ethnic group	Development decisions balance the requirements of different ethnic groups
Gender and development	Depends on perspective	National and sub-national	Moves towards greater gender equity	Approaches vary, but increasingly there is a focus on grassroots participation
Rights-based development	State, NGOs and individuals	Varies	Individuals and groups able to live fulfilled lives	Approaches vary from very small-scale awareness-raising activities to large-scale transnational campaigns
Post-development	Grassroots organizations and individuals	Very small-scale	A dangerous, Eurocentric concept which destroys local cultures and environments	Focus on grassroots activities, local-level participation

Source: (Willis, 2011)

Annex 3 Trends in development theory

Conventional and recent views	Trend	New themes
Grand theories	Differentiation	Middle-range theories, local knowledge
(1) Unreflexive use of language, indicators, models; (2) discourse analysis	Reflexivity, self-questioning	Development as social learning, social feedbacks, reflexive development
Sectoral theories. Gap between economic and social/political development. (Multi)disciplinary case studies, policies.	Interdisciplinarity	Bridging approaches (new institutional economics, sociology of economics) and themes (embeddedness, social capital, social economy, holism)
State-, market- or society-led development	Intersectoral cooperation	Intersectoral synergies. Public action
Homogenization, essentialism	Diversity	Politics of difference
(1) Betting on the strong; (2) humanitarian assistance, from relief to development	Human security	Risks of polarization, global social policy, global social contract
(1) Gender blind; (2) WID (Women in Development) (add women and stir)	Gender awareness	Gender interests, gendering development
(1) Mastery over nature; (2) sustainable development (add environment and stir)	Environment	Green GDP, political ecology
(1) Westernization; (2) homogenization vs. indigenization (add culture and stir)	Cultural turn	Diversity and cultural capital as political currency, (3) as growth pole
(1) Nation; (2) local	Unit of development	Regional and world development and multiscalar partnerships

Source: (Nederveen Pieterse, 2010)

Annex 4 LEADER development

Stage	Duration	Funds	Budget (EUR)	LAGs
Leader I	1991–1993	EAGGF-Guidance, ESF, ERDF	450 million	217
Leader II	1994-1999	EAGGF-Guidance, ESF, ERDF	1.7 billion	821
Leader+	2000-2006	EAGGF-Guidance	2.1 billion	893 in EU-15 (+ 250 in the Leader+type measure 2004-2006) in 6 MS
„Leader axis“	2007-2013	EAFRD	5.5 billion → 6% of the EAFRD funding	2 200 in EU-27
CLLD	2014-2020	CSF Funds	Min. 5% of EAFRD + ???	3 000?

Source : ELARD, 2014

Annex 5 Definitions of local and regional development

Organisation	Type	Definition
Institute of Economic Development	Professional Association (UK)	A set of policies and actions designed to improve the performance of a spatially defined economy for the benefit of all residents.
International Labour Organisation (ILO)	United Nations agency	Local economic development (LED) is a strategy for employment promotion through micro and small enterprise development, support of social dialogue and development planning.
Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	International organisation	The purpose of local development is to build the capacity of a defined area to improve its economic future and the quality of life for inhabitants. Regional development is a broad term but can be seen as a general effort to reduce regional disparities by supporting (employment and wealth-generating) economic activities in regions.
Regional Development Agencies	Non-departmental public bodies (UK)	The RDAs use regeneration to turn around local economies, lever in investment in both urban and rural settings and raise aspirations. They work with partners to improve the quality of the environment, revitalise communities, create more jobs, provide more skills, and improve transport and communications infrastructure.
World Bank	International financial institution	The purpose of local economic development (LED) is to build up the economic capacity of a local area to improve its economic future and the quality of life for all.

Source: (Pike et al., 2017a)

Annex 6 Old and new paradigms of regional development

	Old paradigm	New paradigm
Objectives	Compensating temporarily for location disadvantages of lagging regions	Tapping underutilised potential in all regions for enhancing regional competitiveness
Unit of intervention	Administrative units	Functional economic areas
Strategies	Sectoral approach	Integrated development projects
Tools	Subsidies and state aids	Mix of soft and hard capital (capital stock, labour market, business environment, social capital and networks)
Actors	Central government	Different levels of government

Source: OECD, 2011

Annex 7 Top–down and bottom-up approaches

Top-down approaches	Bottom-up approaches
1. Top-down approach in which decisions about the areas where intervention is needed are taken in the national centre	1. Promotion of development in all territories with the initiative often coming from below
2. Managed by the national central administration	2. Decentralised, vertical cooperation between different tiers of government and horizontal co-operation between public and private bodies
3. Sectoral approach to development	3. Territorial approach to development (locality, milieu)
4. Development of large industrial projects, that will foster other economic activity	4. Use of the development potential of each area, in order to stimulate a progressive adjustment of the local economic system to the changing economic environment
5. Financial support, incentives and subsidies, as the main factor of attraction of economic activity	5. Provision of key conditions for the development of economic activity

Source: (Pike et al., 2017a)

Annex 8 Rural policy 3.0

	Old paradigm	New Rural Paradigm (2006)	Rural Policy 3.0: Implementing the New Rural Paradigm
Objectives	Equalisation	Competitiveness	Well-being considering multiple dimensions of: 1) the economy; 2) society; and 3) the environment
Policy focus	Support for a single dominant resource sector	Support for multiple sectors based on their competitiveness	Low-density economies differentiated by type of rural area
Tools	Subsidies for firms	Investments in qualified firms and communities	Integrated rural development approach – spectrum of support to public sector, firms and third sector
Key actors and stakeholders	Farm organisations and national governments	All levels of government and all relevant departments plus local stakeholders	Involvement of: 1) public sector – multi-level governance; 2) private sector – for-profit firms and social enterprise; 3) third sector – non-governmental organisations and civil society
Policy approach	Uniformly applied top-down policy	Bottom-up policy, local strategies	Integrated approach with multiple policy domains
Rural definition	Not urban	Rural as a variety of distinct types of place	Three types of rural: 1) within a functional urban area; 2) close to a functional urban area; 3) far from a functional urban area

Source: (OECD, 2019)

Annex 9 EDORA cube

Figure 2: The EDORA Cube – a 3 dimensional framework for analysis

Note: IA = Intermediate Accessible, IR = Intermediate Remote
 PRA= Predominantly Rural Accessible PRR = Predominantly Rural Remote

Source: (Loibl et al., 2008)

Annex 10 Urban rural policentricity

Urban mono-centric	Urban poly-centric	Peri-urban mono-centric	Peri-urban poly-centric	Deep rural
1.0, 1.1	2	1.2	3	4

Avots: (Loibl et al., 2008)

Annex 11 Rurality according with Aggregate Geographic Zones and Rural Typology Zones

Fig. 5. (A) (Left) Final map with nine rurality classes based on Economic Density and Accessibility for each Aggregate Geographic Zone (AGZ) (Alpine, Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean and North) derived from the 13 Environmental Zones of Metzger et al. (2005a,b), (B) (Right) Map of the three Rural Typology zones; Peri-Urban, Rural and Deep Rural within the five Aggregate Environmental Zones; Alpine, Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean and North.

Source : (Van Eupen et al., 2012)

Annex 12 Defining urban – rural typologies

Source: European Commission, Eurostat 2018

Annex 13 EUROSTAT territorial typology

	Geographical level	Basic territorial typologies	Urban typologies	Coastal typology	Border typology	Island typology	Mountain typology
Regional typologies:	NUTS 1 regions						
	NUTS 2 regions						
	NUTS 3 regions	Urban-rural typology: predominantly urban regions; intermediate regions; predominantly rural regions	Metropolitan regions	Coastal regions	Border regions	Island regions	Mountain regions
Local typologies:	Local administrative units (LAU)	Degree of urbanisation (*): cities; towns and suburbs; rural areas	City definitions: cities; functional urban areas (FUA) = cities and their commuting zones	Coastal areas			
Grid typologies:	Grid cells (1 km ²)	Cluster types: urban centre; urban clusters; rural grid cells	Urban clusters and urban centres				

Key:

	Individual codes and labels (based on geographical entity)
	Three categories per country (aggregated)
	Combination of individual codes and aggregation
	Two categories per country (aggregated)
	Technical level
	As defined in Regulation (EC) No 1059/2003 on the establishment of a common classification of territorial units for statistics (NUTS).

(*) Within the degree of urbanisation typology the aggregation of cities with towns and suburbs is referred to as urban areas.

Source: Eurostat 2018

Annex 14 Pilots classifications

Pilots	NUTS policy pilots	NUTS regions	OECD urban-rural types (Drijkstra, Poelman)	PLUREL RUR delineation and morphology	EDORA structural typology	FAROEU Rural Typology zones	JRC rural typology	EUROSTAT other classifications	EUROSTAT DEGURBA LAU level	EUROSTAT urban-rural typology	D4.5 development classification
Flanders	NUTS1	NUTS1	Predominantly urban	Monocentric large, dispersed polycentric	Periurban region	Periurban, Rural	Urban-closed space region	Border region, Coastal region	Towns and suburbs,	Intermediate region, predominantly urban	Regions with strong socio-economic growth
Monaghan	LAU	LAU	Predominantly remote	Rural	Consumption countryside	Deep rural	Rural peripheral region	Border region, Island region, Coastal region	Rural areas	Predominantly rural	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Segóbriga/Cuenca	LAU	NUTS3	Predominantly remote	Rural	Agrarian	Deep rural	Rural peripheral region	Sparsely populated	Rural areas	Predominantly rural	Regions with moderate socio-economic growth
Vidzeme	NUTS3	NUTS3	Predominantly remote	Rural	Agrarian	Deep rural	Rural peripheral region	Border region	Rural areas	Predominantly rural	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Mazowieckie	NUTS2	NUTS2	Intermediate close to city	Monocentric very large	Agrarian	Periurban, Rural	Intermediate closed-space region		Rural areas, towns and suburbs	Intermediate region	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Central Bohemian Region	NUTS2	NUTS2	Intermediate close to city	Monocentric very large	Diversified	Periurban, Rural	Intermediate closed-space region		Rural areas	Predominantly urban	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale

Slovakia	NUTS1	NUTS1	Intermediate close to city, Predominantly rural close to city		Diversified, Consumption countryside	Deep rural/Rural	Intermediate closed-space region, rural accessible region	Border region, Mountain region	Rural areas, towns and suburbs	Intermediate region, Predominantly rural	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Häme	NUTS3	NUTS3	Predominantly rural close to city	Monocentric-medium	Consumption countryside	Deep rural/Rural	Rural accessible region		Rural areas, towns and suburbs	Intermediate region	Regions with strong socio-economic growth
Central Greece	NUTS1	NUTS1	Predominantly remote	Rural	Agrarian	Deep rural/Rural	Rural peripheral region, urban-closed space region	Coastal region	Rural areas, towns and suburbs	Predominantly rural	Regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale
Apulia	NUTS2	NUTS2	Predominantly urban	Monocentric medium, dispersed polycentric	Periurban region	Periurban, Rural	Urban-open space region	Border region, Mountain region, Coastal region	Towns and suburbs	Predominantly urban	Regions with moderate socio-economic growth
Gevgelija - Strumica / North Macedonia	LAU	NUTS1	X	x	x	Deep rural	x	Border region	Rural areas	Intermediate region	x
Galilee	X	X	X	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Source: Own elaborated based on different sources

